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Master Thesis

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Potentials of Onshore Wind Energy in Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria's persistent electricity shortage continues to hinder industrial growth and economic development despite the country's abundant natural resources. This study investigates the potential of onshore wind energy as a sustainable option for addressing Nigeria's electricity deficit and reducing dependence on fossil fuels. The research combines geospatial mapping, techno-economic modelling, and policy assessment to evaluate the feasibility of wind energy development across Nigeria's 36 states. Using data from the Global Wind Atlas, ERA5 reanalysis, and SRTM Digital Elevation Models, a GIS-based Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) was conducted to identify suitable regions for wind farm installations. A case study of the Lambar Rimi Wind Farm in Katsina State further explores technical and financial viability through energy yield estimation and economic performance indicators such as levelised cost of energy (LCOE), net present value (NPV), and internal rate of return (IRR).

Results indicate that northern states such as Katsina and Sokoto exhibit mean wind speeds exceeding 7 m/s at 100 m hub height, making them prime locations for large-scale wind deployment. The expansion scenario at Lambar Rimi demonstrates favourable outcomes, with a 28% capacity factor, LCOE of 0.085 USD/kWh, and an internal rate of return of 15% under blended financing assumptions. However, challenges such as weak grid infrastructure, policy inconsistencies, and solar-biased incentives continue to limit progress. Addressing these issues through targeted wind policies, investment incentives, and grid modernization could unlock an estimated 3.2 GW of viable onshore wind capacity.

This study concludes that onshore wind energy represents a technically and economically feasible pathway for Nigeria's energy transition and climate goals. By promoting community-based wind projects and adopting elements of Germany's Bürgerwindpark model, Nigeria can enhance energy access, create employment, and advance towards its net-zero emission target by 2060.

Keywords: onshore wind potential, GIS-MCDA, techno-economic analysis, renewable policy, community wind farms

Table of Contents

List of Tables	viii
List of Abbreviations / Notations	ix
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Research Objective	4
1.2 Value and Target Audience	4
1.3 Scope and Constraints	5
1.4 Structure of the Document	5
2 Literature Review	7
2.1 Terminology & Definitions	7
2.2 Theoretical Background	8
2.3 Existing Models for Assessing Wind Energy Potential	10
2.4 Case Studies	11
2.5 Scenario Description	12
3 Research Design and Methodology	13
3.1 Population and Sampling	14
3.2 Analysis and Synthesis	16
3.3 Validity and Reliability	20
3.4 Methodological Constraints	20
3.5 Ethical Considerations	21
4 Comprehensive Wind Farm Project Analysis: Technical, Economic and Implementation Framework	23
4.1 Technical Analysis of the Lambar Rimi Wind Farm Project	23
4.1.1 Site selection	23
4.1.1.1 Environmental criteria	23
4.1.1.2 Orography Criteria	26
4.1.1.3 Location criteria	26
4.1.1.4 Climatology criteria	28
4.1.2 Turbine selection	28
4.1.3 Turbine siting	29

4.1.3.1	Energy yield and losses	30
4.2	Wind Farm Economic Viability and Analysis	32
4.2.1	Wind Farm Structure	32
4.2.2	Economic Analysis Framework	33
4.2.2.1	Cash Flow Analysis	34
4.3	Policy and Regulatory Framework Analysis	35
4.3.1	The Nigerian Renewable Energy Policy Landscape	36
4.3.2	International Best Practice: The German Bürgerwindpark (Citizen Wind Farm) Model	38
4.3.3	Analysis and Identification of Actionable Policy Gaps	40
4.4	A Framework for the Adaptation of a Community Based Wind Energy Model in Nigeria	40
4.4.1	Conceptual Foundation and Rationale for Adaptation	41
4.4.2	Adaptation Methodology	41
4.4.3	Phased Implementation Framework	42
4.4.4	Essential Government Enablers	43
5	Results & Discussion	44
5.1	National Wind Resource Potential and Suitability Zoning	44
5.2	Techno-Economic Feasibility of the Lambar Rimi Case Study	46
5.2.1	Wind Resource Characterisation	46
5.2.2	Statistical Analysis of the Wind Regime	47
5.2.3	Energy Yield Estimation	49
5.2.4	Financial Feasibility Analysis	49
5.3	Policy Benchmarking and Community Wind Model Adaptation	49
5.4	Integrated Discussion: Barriers and Opportunities	51
5.4.1	Infrastructural and Regulatory Barriers	51
5.4.2	Security and Socio-Political Challenges	53
5.4.3	Financial Constraints and Market Dynamics	55
5.4.4	The Case for Hybrid Wind-Solar Systems	55
5.4.5	Social and Institutional Opportunities	56
5.4.6	Strategic Outlook	56
5.5	Synopsis	57
6	Conclusion	59

6.1	Critical Reflection	59
6.2	Recommendations for Future Research	60
	References	62

List of Figures

Figure 1-1 Energy and emissions indicators: (a) CO ₂ emissions (Nigeria), (b) electricity access (Nigeria), (c) carbon intensity, (d) wind energy share in Africa ^[11]	2
Figure 1-2 Wind speed distribution across Nigeria at 10m height ^[20]	3
Figure 1-3 Structure of the Master Thesis	6
Figure 2-1 An air parcel moving towards a wind turbine ^[29]	9
Figure 3-1 Research framework for assessing onshore wind energy potential using GIS-MCDA and a site-specific case study approach.	14
Figure 3-2 Map of Nigeria by a. Land size in km ² b. Human Population	15
Figure 3-3 Wind speed distribution at 100m and population density map	17
Figure 3-4 Weighted scores based on roughness and slope	18
Figure 3-5 Weighted scores based on Windspeed and Terrain	19
Figure 3-6 Workflow of the GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis used to generate the wind energy suitability map	22
Figure 4-1 Land Use Map of Katsina State, Nigeria	24
Figure 4-2 Land Use Map of Rimi, Katsina State	25
Figure 4-3 Topography and Orography Conditions of the Rimi Wind Farm	26
Figure 4-4 Wind Farm Proximity to Assess Roads	27
Figure 4-5 Proximity to Electricity Grid	27
Figure 4-6 Generalized Wind Climate (GWC) Data	28
Figure 4-7 Wind farm with optimum spacing	29
Figure 4-8 Typical Onshore wind farm installed cost breakdown ^[6]	33
Figure 4-9 The Cash Flow of the wind farm (170 MW)	35
Figure 4-10 Existing and Planned Transmission Network of the Nigerian Grid	38
Figure 4-11 Conceptual Overview of the Bürgerwindpark	39
Figure 4-12 Comparative framework of wind energy policy in Germany and Nigeria, highlighting differences in financial mechanisms, community participation, grid integration, permitting processes, and policy continuity.	40

Figure 4-13 Conceptual framework illustrating the adaptation of Bürgerwindpark principles from Germany to the Nigerian context through governance, financing, regulatory, and benefit distribution mechanisms.	41
Figure 4-14 Phased Implementation Framework	42
Figure 4-15 Phased Implementation Roadmap for the Nigerian Community Wind Model	43
Figure 5-1 National Onshore Wind Energy Suitability Map of Nigeria (MCDA Result).	45
Figure 5-2 (a) Daily variation of wind speed at 150 m and (b) monthly average wind speed showing a bathtub profile over the study period.	47
Figure 5-3 Weibull probability distribution fit	48
Figure 5-4 Probability Density Function and Cumulative Density Function chart	48
Figure 5-5 Annual and Hourly duration curve	48
Figure 5-6 Barriers affecting the proposed wind farm	52
Figure 5-7 Solutions to the barriers	54
Figure 6-1 Turbulence created by an obstruction ^[27]	72
Figure 6-2 The acceleration effect over ridges ^[36]	73
Figure 6-3 Biological rating scales for the wind speed ^{[37], [38]}	77

List of Tables

Table 2-1 Definitions of key technical and economic terms used in this thesis.	7
Table 2-2 Main categories of models used in wind energy potential assessment	10
Table 2-3 Comparative Case Studies of Wind Energy Development Models	12
Table 2-4 Summary of Onshore Wind Energy Development Scenarios for Nigeria (2025–2040)	12
Table 3-1 Materials and Data Sources Used in the Study	20
Table 4-1 Sensitivity on diameter spacing	30
Table 4-2 Wind farm energy yield report	30
Table 4-3 Additional technical losses applicable for wind farm siting	31
Table 4-4 Energy Yield calculation	32
Table 4-5 Summary of Key Economic Inputs and Results	34
Table 4-6 Inputs and Outputs of the cash flow model	35
Table 4-7 Policy Evolution in Nigeria's Renewable Energy Sector	36
Table 5-1 Summary of MCDA-Based Wind Energy Suitability Classes in Nigeria.	46

List of Abbreviations / Notations

Abbreviation	Full Form
AEP	Annual Energy Production
AEPG	Annual Energy Production Gross
AfDP	African Development Bank
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
BOM	Bill of Materials
BOI	Bank of Industry
BWK	Bürgerwindpark (Citizen Wind Farm)
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
Co. KGs	Compagnie Kommanditgesellschaft
CF	Capacity Factor; Cash Flow
CF _{net}	Net Capacity Factor
CFM	Cash Flow Model
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CRF	Capital Recovery Factor
CRU	Climatic Recovery Factor
DAAD	Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst
DCF	Discounted Cash Flow
DCCF	Discounted Cumulative Cash Flow
DEMs	Digital Elevation Models
DFIs	Development Finance Institutions
DisCos	Distribution Companies
DSCR	Debt-Service Coverage Ratio
D	Rotor Diameter
ECN	Energy Commission of Nigeria
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EEG	Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (Renewable Energy Sources Act)
EIA	Energy Information Administration
EPC	Engineering, Procurement and Construction
ERA5	ECMWF Reanalysis v5
ETP	Energy Transition Plan
FCT	Federal Capital Territory
FiT	Feed-in Tariff
FMP	Federal Ministry of Power
GCF	Green Climate Fund
GWh	Gigawatt-hour
GE	General Electric

GIS	Geographic Information Systems
GmbH	Gesellschaft mit beschränkter Haftung
GW	Gigawatt
GWC	Generalized Wind Climate
H	Hub Height
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPP	Independent Power Producer
IPPs	Independent Power Producers
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy
LGA	Local Government Area
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
m/s	Meters per second
MW	Megawatts
NBET	Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading Plc
NBS	National Bureau of Statistics
NEP	National Electrification Project
NERC	National Electricity Regulatory Commission
NiMet	Nigerian Meteorological Agency
NIEP	National Integrated Energy Policy
NIMBY	Not In My Backyard
NPV	Net Present Value
NREEEP	National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy
O&M	Operations and Maintenance
OnSSET	Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
P ₅₀	P ₅₀ Energy Yield (50% probability of exceedance)
P ₉₀	P ₉₀ Energy Yield (90% probability of exceedance)
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PDF	Probability Density Function
PMI	Project Management Institute
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement
PVC	Present Value of Cost
PMI	Project Management Institute
PWC	PriceWaterhouseCoopers
PWh	Petawatt-hour
QGIS	Quantum Geographic Information System

RE	Renewable Energy
REA	Rural Electrification Agency
REDZ	Renewable Energy Deployment Zone
REIPPPP	Renewable Energy Independent Power Producer Procurement Programme
REMP	Renewable Energy Master Plan
ROI	Return on Investment
SAM	System Advisor Model
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
SPV	Special Purpose Vehicle
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threat analysis
TCN	Transmission Company of Nigeria
TWh	Terawatt-hours
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
USD	United States Dollar
WAsP	Wind Atlas Analysis and Application Program
W/m ²	Watts per square meter
WT	Wind Turbine
WTG	Wind Turbine Generator
eG	eingetragene Genossenschaft

Latin Symbols

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
A	Cross sectional area of the rotor	m ²
A	Scale parameter	m/s
C ₀	Initial investment cost	\$
C _t	Net cash flow in year t	\$
C _t	Cost at time t	
D	Rotor diameter	m
d _t	Differential time	s
D _x	Wake diameter at distance x	m
E _{ann}	Annual Energy Production	MWh
E _t	Energy generated in year t	MWh
F	Thrust Force	N
F _t	Fuel costs in year t (typically zero for wind)	\$
H	Hub height	m
I ₀	Initial investment	\$
I _t	Investment costs (e.g. turbine purchase) in year t	\$
k	Shape Parameter	m ²
m	Mass of air	kg
M	Molar mass of air	kg/mol
M _t	Operation and maintenance cost in year t	\$
n	Moles	
n	Project lifetime/number of observations	years/-
P	Pressure	Pa
P	Power output	W
P _{rated}	Rated power	MW
r	Discount rate (5 – 10%)	%
R	Universal Gas Constant	J/molK
R	Rotor radius	m
t	Lifetime (20 – 25 years)	years
T	Temperature	K
T	Torque	Nm
U ₀	Free stream wind speed	m/s
U _x	Wind speed at a distance x downstream	
v	Volume of air parcel	m ²
v _i	Individual wind speed <i>i</i>	m/s
x	Downstream distance	
V _m	Mean wind speed	m/s
Z	Elevation	m

Greek Symbols

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
α	Terrain exponent (power law for height extrapolation)	-
ρ	Air density	kg/m ³
σ	Standard deviation of wind speeds	m/s

Dimensionless Metrics

Symbol	Meaning	Unit
A	Axial induction factor	-
C _P	Power coefficient (efficiency ratio)	-
K	Weibull shape factor, Wake decay constant	-

1 Introduction

Access to sustainable and affordable energy is a crucial factor for economic growth, industrialization, and social development worldwide. Yet, in many developing countries, inadequate and unreliable energy supply remains a critical barrier to progress ^[1]. Globally, electricity demand has increased steadily over the past four decades, driven by rapid population growth, urbanization, and industrial expansion. However, this growth has been accompanied by profound challenges. Heavy reliance on fossil fuels (coal, oil and natural gas) has raised concerns about fossil fuel depletion, price volatility, and climate change ^[1].

Current global electricity generation trend is characterized by both supply challenges and significant emissions. Around 30,000 TWh is produced annually, meeting only 16.7% of global energy demand, with over 60% of electricity generated from fossil fuel ^[2]. Although renewable sources like hydropower, wind and solar are growing, fossil fuels remain the backbone of electricity generation, contributing to rising global emissions, now exceeding 35 billion tonnes annually (Figure 1-1 a) ^[3, 2].

Nigeria, Africa's most populous nation with over 220 million people ^[4], faces severe energy insecurity. Despite abundant fossil fuel reserves, over 40% of Nigerians still lack access to electricity (Figure 1-1 b), and those with access often experience unreliable supply ^[5]. Electricity consumption has grown rapidly, reaching just above 500 TWh in 2023, yet actual generation capacity lags far behind with only 40.7 TWh in 2023 ^[6]. Chronic underperformance of power plants, grid limitations, seasonal hydropower fluctuations, and high system losses have left households and industries dependent on costly, polluting generators ^[6].

Natural gas dominates Nigeria's power sector, accounting for 70-77% of grid electricity in recent years. While gas-based generation has expanded steadily, this overdependence exposes the economy to global fuel price volatility and worsens environmental sustainability challenges, as carbon intensity from power generation continues to rise (Figure 1-1 c) ^[10, 11].

In this context, diversifying the energy mix is essential. Wind energy offers significant opportunities. According to IRENA, Nigeria's technical onshore potential is about 3.2 GW, based on using only 1% of suitable land ^[7]. Wind resources are unevenly distributed. Northern states such as Katsina, Sokoto as well as Borno record average wind speeds above 7 m/s, suitable for utility-scale projects ^[8]. By contrast, southern states typically have lower speeds of 2–4 m/s, better suited for small-scale

or hybrid systems (Figure 1-2). Coastal states, including Lagos, Delta and Bayelsa, also show promise but require further mapping [9].

Despite this potential, Nigeria’s wind sector remains underdeveloped. The only large-scale project to date, the 10 MW Lambar Rimi Wind Farm in Katsina, faced prolonged delays due to insecurity, mismanagement, and funding gaps. It became partially operational in 2020 but was soon shut down [12]. More recently a \$500 million hybrid wind-solar initiative was announced in April 2025 aiming to electrify an additional 4,400 households[13]. These limited experiences reveal both the opportunities and challenges of scaling up wind energy in Nigeria [12]

Figure 1-1 Energy and emissions indicators: (a) CO₂ emissions (Nigeria), (b) electricity access (Nigeria), (c) carbon intensity, (d) wind energy share in Africa [11]

Government policy frameworks, including the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP), the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP), and the Energy Transition Plan (ETP), aim to increase the renewables’ share in electricity generation from 13% in 2015 to 36% by 2030, and to achieve net-zero emissions by

2060 [7, 14, 15]. However, implementation has been inconsistent, with solar energy attracting more investment than wind.

Beyond energy security, wind energy offers economic and industrial opportunities. The global wind market is projected to reach \$318 billion by 2034, with more than 1,000 GW of new capacity expected by 2030 [17]. Nigeria’s mineral resources, such as iron ore, could support local manufacturing of turbine components, create jobs and attract investment while positioning the country as a renewable energy hub in West Africa [18, 19].

While Nigeria’s wind energy potential is well acknowledged in policy documents and international roadmaps, major research and deployment gaps persist. Existing Nigerian studies often focus on single sites, rely heavily on limited meteorological data, and lack integration of geospatial mapping, techno-economic feasibility, and policy analysis. State-level assessments remain incomplete, particularly in southern and coastal regions. Few studies evaluate financial viability using key indicators such as Net Present Value (NPV) or Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE), and regulatory frameworks are rarely benchmarked against international best practices such as Germany’s community-based Bürgerwindpark model [21]. Hybrid systems where wind complements other renewables are also under explored.

Figure 1-2 Wind speed distribution across Nigeria at 10m height [20]

This thesis seeks to fill these gaps through a comprehensive, data-driven approach that integrates geospatial analysis, high-resolution wind datasets, techno-economic modelling, and policy benchmarking. By doing so, it will generate actionable insights into Nigeria's wind energy potential, informing policy, guiding investment, and contributing to the broader goal of building a resilient, renewable-based energy system.

1.1 Research Objective

The aim of this study is to evaluate the technical, economic, and regulatory potential of onshore wind energy as a sustainable pathway for addressing Nigeria's electricity deficit and diversifying its energy mix.

1. Assess the spatial distribution of wind energy resources across Nigeria's 36 states using GIS mapping and ERA5 reanalysis data, identifying regions most suitable for utility-scale and decentralized wind energy projects.
2. Evaluate the techno-economic feasibility of wind energy deployment by simulating key financial and performance indicators including capacity factor, Net Present Value (NPV), Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), Capital Expenditure (CAPEX), and Operational Expenditure (OPEX).
3. Analyse Nigeria's legal and regulatory framework for renewable energy and benchmark it against international best practices, with reference to Germany's Leitfaden-Bürgerwindpark model, to identify gaps in policy, grid integration, and financing mechanisms for wind projects.
4. To identify barriers and opportunities for large-scale wind energy deployment, focusing on issues such as grid limitations, financing constraints, social acceptance and infrastructure deficits, while highlighting opportunities for local manufacturing, foreign investment and hybrid systems.
5. Propose strategic policy and investment recommendations to accelerate wind energy adoption in Nigeria, supporting the national goals of increasing renewable energy share and achieving net-zero emissions by 2060.

1.2 Value and Target Audience

By addressing Nigeria's energy access gap with actionable strategies for wind energy adoption, this study provides valuable guidance for government, investors, academia, and development partners, while ultimately advancing socio-economic development and environmental sustainability.

1.3 Scope and Constraints

Following the national and regional wind resource assessment, this thesis conducts an in-depth case study of the Lambar Rimi site in Katsina State, the most significant onshore wind project site in Nigeria to date. The objective is to evaluate the technical and economic feasibility of expanding the existing wind farm and to identify candidate expansion areas nearby using secondary data sources. The analysis relies primarily on open and reanalysis datasets (ERA5, Global Wind Atlas), GIS spatial layers (land use, slope, protected areas, grid lines, roads), and techno-economic simulations implemented in Microsoft excel. No onsite anemometry data are available. The results are explicitly presented as indicative and conditional, with clear recommendations for on-site measurement (met mast or LiDAR) prior to any investment decision.

1.4 Structure of the Document

The thesis is organised into six chapters, each addressing a key component of the research. The overall structure of the study is illustrated in Figure 1-3. The study is organised into six chapters, each addressing a key component of the investigation.

Chapter 1 introduces the research topic, outlines the motivation for the study, and presents the research objectives and questions. Chapter 2 provides a comprehensive literature review covering key terminology and definitions, the theoretical background of wind energy, existing models for assessing wind energy potential, relevant international and African case studies, and scenario descriptions for onshore wind development in Nigeria.

Chapter 3 presents the national assessment, where the broader contextual background relevant to the study is analysed. Chapter 4 forms the core of the thesis and presents the comprehensive analysis. This chapter integrates multiple analytical dimensions, including technical analysis, economic evaluation, and policy considerations. The technical analysis includes aspects such as site selection, system configuration, energy yield assessment, and layout considerations. The economic analysis evaluates cost structures, levelized cost of energy (LCOE), net present value (NPV), internal rate of return (IRR), and financial feasibility. In addition, the policy framework and practical implementation guidelines are examined to bridge technical and institutional considerations.

Chapter 5 presents the results and discusses the findings obtained from the integrated analyses. Finally, Chapter 6 summarises the main conclusions of the research and provides recommendations for future work and practical implementation.

Figure 1-3 Structure of the Master Thesis

2 Literature Review

The literature review is structured to provide a systematic foundation for the assessment of wind energy potential in Nigeria. It begins with a clarification of terminology and definitions relevant to energy demand, electricity generation, and wind resource assessment. The chapter then discusses the theoretical background of wind energy, examines existing models and methodologies, reviews case studies of wind energy development both globally and within Nigeria, and concludes with scenario descriptions that highlight gaps in knowledge and opportunities for further research. The literature was selected based on three criteria: (1) relevance to renewable energy and wind energy studies in Nigeria and comparable developing countries, (2) credibility of sources such as peer-reviewed journals, government policy documents, and reports by international organizations (IEA, IRENA, World Bank, AfDB), and (3) recency, prioritizing publications within the last ten years while including earlier foundational works where necessary.

2.1 Terminology & Definitions

This section defines key technical and economic terms used throughout the thesis to ensure clarity and consistency. The definitions are based on literature and standards relevant to wind energy and power systems (Table 2-1).

Table 2-1 Definitions of key technical and economic terms used in this thesis.

Term	Definition	Ref.
Electricity Demand (MW)	Total electrical energy required by consumers within a defined system over a specified period.	[21, 22, 23]
Electricity Generation Capacity (MW)	Maximum electrical power that installed generation units can produce under specified conditions.	[10]
Available Capacity (MW)	Portion of installed generation capacity that is operational and available for dispatch after accounting for outages and constraints.	[10]
Renewable Energy	Energy derived from naturally replenishing sources such as wind, solar, hydro, biomass, and geothermal.	[23, 30, 24]
Wind Energy	Conversion of the kinetic energy of moving air into mechanical or electrical energy using wind turbines.	[24, 8]
Wind Speed (m/s)	Rate of horizontal air movement measured at a specified height above ground level.	[24]
Hub Height (m)	Vertical distance between the ground and the centre of a wind turbine rotor.	[24]

Term	Definition	Ref.
Cut-in Speed (m/s)	Minimum wind speed at which a turbine begins generating electrical power.	[22, 24]
Cut-out Speed (m/s)	Maximum wind speed at which a turbine shuts down to prevent mechanical damage.	[32, 24]
Power Curve	Relationship between wind speed at hub height and the electrical power output of a wind turbine.	[22, 24]
Weibull Distribution	Statistical distribution commonly used to model wind speed frequency and variability.	[24, 33]
Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE)	Discounted average cost of electricity generation over a power plant's lifetime, calculated as the ratio of total lifetime costs to total lifetime energy production.	[34, 35]
Net Present Value (NPV)	Financial metric representing the difference between the present value of cash inflows and outflows over a project's lifetime.	[36]
Capacity Factor (CF)	Ratio of actual energy produced by a power plant to the maximum possible energy output at continuous full-rated capacity.	[17]
P50/P90 Energy Yield	Statistical energy production estimates representing 50% and 90% probability of exceedance, respectively.	[37]
Wake Effects	Reduction in wind speed and increase in turbulence downstream of a wind turbine due to energy extraction from the wind.	[38, 30]
Jensen (Park) Model	Analytical wake model used for preliminary wind farm layout optimisation based on linear wake expansion.	[39, 40]
Bürgerwindpark	Community-owned wind farm development model based on local financial participation and shared ownership.	[20, 26]
Blended Finance	Financing approach combining concessional public capital with private investment to reduce project risk.	[27]
Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV)	Legally independent entity established to develop, own, and operate a specific project while isolating financial risk.	[29, 28]

2.2 Theoretical Background

Wind energy is derived from the kinetic energy of moving air masses generated by atmospheric pressure gradients caused by uneven solar heating of the Earth's sur-

face (Figure 2-1). Wind turbines convert a portion of this kinetic energy into mechanical power, which is subsequently transformed into electrical energy through a generator ^[29, 40].

The theoretical power available in the wind depends primarily on air density, rotor swept area, and wind velocity, with wind speed being the most influential parameter due to its cubic relationship with power output. Consequently, site selection and accurate characterization of wind regimes are critical for reliable wind energy assessment ^[25, 41].

Because wind speed varies stochastically over time, statistical methods are commonly employed to analyse wind regimes and estimate long-term energy yield. Probability distribution models such as the Weibull distribution are widely used to represent wind speed variability, while wake models are applied to account for energy losses within wind farms due to turbine interactions ^[22, 22, 9, 35, 25, 26].

In this thesis, standard wind energy theory and analytical models are applied to estimate wind power potential and energy yield. The detailed mathematical formulations and derivations of the governing equations are provided in Appendix A.

The Energy available in wind is kinetic energy of large masses of air moving over the earth's surface ^[29]. The blades of the wind turbine receive this kinetic energy, which is then transformed to mechanical or electrical forms, depending on our end use ^[40]. The efficiency of converting wind to other useful energy forms greatly depends on the efficiency with which the rotor interacts with the wind stream ^[29].

Figure 2-1 An air parcel moving towards a wind turbine ^[29]

2.3 Existing Models for Assessing Wind Energy Potential

Wind energy potential has been assessed using a variety of modelling approaches that differ in complexity, data requirements, and spatial resolution. In the literature, these approaches can be broadly grouped into statistical, geospatial (GIS-based), and integrated techno-economic models. Table 2-2 summarises the main categories of models used in wind energy potential assessment, highlighting their inputs, strengths, and limitations.

Table 2-2 Main categories of models used in wind energy potential assessment

Model Category	Typical Methods/Tools	Primary Inputs
¹ Statistical Models	Weibull and Rayleigh distributions; wind speed frequency analysis; power curve integration	Measured or reanalysis wind speed data
² Geospatial (GIS-based) Models	Spatial suitability analysis; land-use and environmental exclusion mapping	Wind maps, land-use data, terrain slope, population density
³ Techno-Economic Models	Levelised cost of electricity (LCOE); financial optimisation; system sizing tools	Capital costs, O&M costs, energy yield, demand profiles
⁴ Integrated Assessment Models	Combination of statistical, GIS-based, and economic methods	Multi-source datasets (resource, spatial, economic)

Early assessments at global and regional scales primarily relied on statistical models, most based on Weibull or Rayleigh wind speed distributions combined with turbine power curves. These methods demonstrated that the theoretical and technical potential of onshore wind energy is very large, even after accounting for land-use exclusions and wake losses. However, such approaches provide limited spatial detail and do not adequately address economic feasibility or grid integration considerations [42, 43].

To address these limitations, GIS-based models were introduced, integrating wind resource data with spatial constraints such as land use, terrain, environmental restrictions, population density, and proximity to transmission infrastructure. These methods have been widely applied in continental and national-scale studies, partic-

¹ Simple to apply; low data and computational requirements however, limited spatial resolution; weak representation of terrain and land-use effects.

² Improved spatial realism, suitable for regional and national planning however, limited treatment of economic viability and system integration.

³ Decision-oriented; enables economic comparison of alternatives however, high data requirements; sensitive to cost assumptions.

⁴ Comprehensive planning support; suitable for policy and investment analysis however, increased complexity; higher computational and data demands.

ularly in Africa, where they have supported electrification planning and energy system analysis. GIS-based approaches improve spatial realism but often rely on simplified assumptions regarding wind variability, system intermittency, and economic performance^[44, 45].

More recent studies employ integrated techno-economic frameworks, which combine statistical wind resource assessment and geospatial suitability analysis with economic evaluation. These models enable the estimation of indicators such as levelised cost of electricity, optimal turbine selection, and system feasibility, making them more suitable for decision-oriented planning and investment analysis. Such integrated approaches are increasingly common in global and African studies but remain limited in application within many developing countries^[46, 47, 48, 49].

In Nigeria, most existing studies focus on site-specific statistical analyses of wind speed data, predominantly using Weibull-based methods at relatively low measurement heights. While these studies provide useful local insights, they are generally limited in spatial coverage and rarely incorporate GIS-based multi-criteria analysis or detailed techno-economic modelling. As a result, much of the Nigerian literature remains descriptive and offers limited support for national-scale planning or investment decision-making^[50, 27, 51, 52, 53].

Overall, the literature reveals a clear methodological progression from purely statistical approaches toward integrated spatial and techno-economic frameworks. The limited application of such comprehensive models in Nigeria highlights a research gap that motivates this study, which seeks to combine wind resource assessment, spatial suitability analysis, and economic evaluation to support informed planning and policy development.

2.4 Case Studies

Table 2-3 compares international and African wind energy case studies, illustrating how differing ownership structures and policy frameworks shape deployment outcomes and highlighting Nigeria's early-stage position.

Table 2-3 Comparative Case Studies of Wind Energy Development Models

Country	Development Model	Installed Wind Capacity	Ref
⁵ Germany	Community-owned (Bürgerwindpark)	Above 30 GW	[21]
⁶ Denmark	Cooperative ownership	40 MW	[55]
⁷ China	Centralized, state-led planning	Around 280 GW	[56]
⁸ South Africa	Competitive IPP procurement	Above 3.4 GW	[19]
⁹ Kenya	Utility-scale IPP	310 MW	[49]
¹⁰ Nigeria	Pilot-scale / stalled development	10 MW	[22]

In Africa, about 3% of the total electricity produced is from Wind Energy (see Figure 1-1 d).

2.5 Scenario Description

This section outlines three development pathways for onshore wind energy in Nigeria from 2025 to 2040. The scenarios are designed to contextualize the findings of this research within broader strategic energy planning and are differentiated by the degree of policy commitment, investment intensity, and infrastructure development. The three scenarios considered are Business as Usual (BAU), Moderate Growth, and Advanced Growth.

Table 2-4 Summary of Onshore Wind Energy Development Scenarios for Nigeria (2025–2040)

Scenario	Policy & Regulatory Environment	Installed Capacity by 2040
¹¹ Business as Usual (BAU)	Weak and inconsistent policy support; limited wind-specific incentives	Few Megawatts
¹² Moderate Growth	Partial policy reform; feed-in tariffs; improved permitting	Above 2 GW
¹³ Advanced Growth	Strong political commitment; wind-specific targets; stable regulatory framework	Greater than 5 GW

⁵ Stable long-term policy, citizen financial participation, grid priority access (Onshore wind farms in Schleswig-Holstein and Lower Saxony)

⁶ Early cooperative legislation, strong public support (Middelgrunden Offshore Wind Farm)

⁷ Strong state planning, large-scale grid expansion, economies of scale (Gansu Wind Farm)

⁸ Transparent auctions (REIPPPP), private-sector participation (Cookhouse Wind Farm; Jeffreys Bay Wind Farm)

⁹ International finance, government support, long-term PPA (Lake Turkana Wind Power Project)

¹⁰ Limited policy consistency, grid constraints, security challenges (Katsina Wind Farm)

¹¹ Continued underutilization of wind resources; limited economic and environmental benefits

¹² Establishes wind as a complementary energy source; builds local O&M capacity

¹³ Positions Nigeria as a regional wind energy leader; major economic and climate benefits

3 Research Design and Methodology

This study employed a quantitative, GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) framework to evaluate the suitability of onshore wind energy development across Nigeria. The analysis is conducted at the national scale using raster-based spatial modelling techniques.

The methodology follows a two-phase approach. First, a national-scale geospatial analysis is conducted to identify suitable regions for wind energy development. Second, a site-specific case study of the Lambar Rimi wind farm in Katsina State is performed to assess technical and economic feasibility.

Wind speed data at 100 m height, obtained from the Global Wind Atlas, are used as the primary suitability factor. Topographic parameters, including slope and surface roughness, are derived from Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) data. Population density data are incorporated as a spatial constraint to exclude highly urbanized areas.

All datasets are projected to a common coordinate reference system (WGS 84 / UTM Zone 32N), resampled to a uniform spatial resolution, and converted to raster format. Each criterion is standardized using a five-class scoring system ranging from Very Low (1) to Very High (5). Relative weights are assigned based on their importance to wind energy development, with wind speed given the highest weight.

The standardized criteria are integrated using a weighted linear combination approach to generate a composite suitability index. Areas with high population density and restricted land use are excluded using a binary masking approach. The final suitability index is classified into five categories: Very Low, Low, Moderate, High, and Very High.

Figure 3-1 presents a step-by-step overview of the methodological workflow adopted in this study. The figure summarizes the progression from data collection and national-scale geospatial analysis to site selection and site-specific techno-economic evaluation. While the figure provides a visual guide to the research process, the subsequent sections describe each methodological component in detail.

Figure 3-1 Research framework for assessing onshore wind energy potential using GIS-MCDA and a site-specific case study approach.

3.1 Population and Sampling

The study area for this research encompasses the entire geographical extent of Nigeria, a country with an estimated land area of 923,769 km² and a population exceeding 200 million people. The analysis considers both the physical landscape and population distribution as key factors influencing wind farm siting.

A grid-based sampling approach is adopted, where the study area is divided into uniform spatial units to ensure comprehensive coverage. To account for regional variation, the analysis is further stratified according to Nigeria’s six geopolitical zones: North-West, North-East, North-Central, South-West, South-East, and South-South.

Areas designated as protected, ecologically sensitive, or highly urbanized are excluded from consideration to minimize environmental and social conflicts. Population distribution maps and land availability are used to guide this exclusion process. These spatial characteristics are illustrated in Figure 3-2

Figure 3-2 Map of Nigeria by a. Land size in km² b. Human Population

3.2 Analysis and Synthesis

The analytical process combines descriptive statistics with GIS-based MCDA to evaluate wind energy potential across Nigeria.

Descriptive statistical methods are used to summarize key variables such as wind speed, elevation, slope, and population distribution. Zonal statistics are applied to compute average wind speeds for each state, providing an initial assessment of spatial variability.

Spatial analysis incorporates terrain parameters, including elevation, slope, and surface roughness, which significantly influence wind turbine performance. These variables are integrated using weighted overlay techniques within the GIS environment to generate composite suitability maps.

The resulting suitability index identifies northern regions as the most favourable for wind energy development. These areas are subsequently selected for detailed case study analysis.

The GIS-MCDA workflow and resulting spatial outputs are presented in Figure 3-3 to Figure 3-6.

Figure 3-3 Wind speed distribution at 100m and population density map

Figure 3-4 Weighted scores based on roughness and slope

Weighted scores based on windspeed at 100m

Terrain analysis of Nigerias lands

Figure 3-5 Weighted scores based on Windspeed and Terrain

3.3 Validity and Reliability

The validity of the study is supported using widely recognized and validated secondary datasets, including the Global Wind Atlas and SRTM. The selected evaluation criteria are consistent with established methodologies for wind energy assessment.

The national-scale approach enhances external validity by enabling the findings to be generalized to regions with similar climatic and geographical conditions. The datasets used in this study are summarized in Table 3-1.

Table 3-1 Materials and Data Sources Used in the Study

S/N	Data	Format	Source
1	Wind speed data	Raster/Time series	Global Wind Atlas, NASA Power
2	Digital Elevation Model	Raster	SRTM
3	Land use and cover	Raster	Landsat, Sentinel imagery
4	Surface Roughness	Raster	Landsat
5	Restricted and protected areas	Vector	Nigerian Geospatial Dataset
7	Railway network	Vector	Ministry of Transports
8	Grid Lines	Vector	ENERGYDATA.INFO website (An Innovation of World Bank Group)
9	Population data	Table	National Bureau of Statistics
10	Boundary, Roads, Water bodies, River lines and Settlements	Vector Map	UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) website

3.4 Methodological Constraints

Despite the robustness of the adopted methodology, certain limitations must be acknowledged. The resolution of Digital Elevation Models may not capture fine-scale terrain variations that could influence local wind conditions. Additionally, wind data derived from secondary sources may not fully reflect temporal variability or extreme weather events.

The grid-based analysis assumes uniformity within spatial units, which may overlook sub-grid variability. Furthermore, the absence of site-specific field measurements limits the precision of localized assessments.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

This study does not involve human participants or sensitive personal data. However, the identification of potential wind energy sites has implications for land use and local communities.

To address this, population data are incorporated to avoid densely populated areas, and environmentally sensitive regions are excluded from analysis. All datasets used are publicly available and comply with open-access licensing agreements.

The study adheres to principles of responsible environmental management and equitable development, consistent with international research ethics standards.

Figure 3-6 Workflow of the GIS-based multi-criteria decision analysis used to generate the wind energy suitability map

4 Comprehensive Wind Farm Project Analysis: Technical, Economic and Implementation Framework

4.1 Technical Analysis of the Lambar Rimi Wind Farm Project

Following the national-scale wind resource assessment presented in Chapter 3, a detailed technical, economic, and implementation analysis of a representative wind farm project in Nigeria is conducted. The GIS-based Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) identified northern Nigeria, particularly Katsina, Sokoto, and Jigawa states, as areas with the highest suitability for utility-scale wind energy development.

Katsina State was selected for detailed analysis due to its high wind resource potential (mean wind speeds exceeding 7 m/s at 100 m hub height) and the presence of the existing Lambar Rimi Wind Farm. This enables both validation of the national assessment and evaluation of potential expansion scenarios.

The proposed expansion considered in this study has a capacity of 170 MW. Technical modelling, energy yield estimation, and economic evaluation were conducted using Microsoft Excel in combination with spatial data derived from GIS analysis.

4.1.1 Site selection

Site selection is a critical stage in wind farm development, aimed at maximizing energy yield while minimizing environmental, technical, and economic constraints [60]. In this study, site selection is based on four key criteria: environmental, orography, location, and climatology. A detailed description of the general site selection framework is provided in Appendix C.

4.1.1.1 Environmental criteria

The proposed site is in Rimi, Katsina State, which currently hosts Nigeria's only large-scale wind farm (10 MW). The land use analysis (Figure 4-1 and Figure 4-2) shows a predominance of agricultural land with sparse settlements, making it suitable for wind energy development with minimal land-use conflict.

The site demonstrates strong potential for expansion due to its low environmental constraints and compatibility with existing land use.

Landuse map of Katsina State, Nigeria

Figure 4-1 Land Use Map of Katsina State, Nigeria

Figure 4-2 Land Use Map of Rimi, Katsina State

4.1.1.2 Orography Criteria

Terrain characteristics significantly influence wind flow and turbine performance. The site exhibits relatively flat terrain with low slope values, making it suitable for wind farm development. Slopes exceeding 30% are avoided due to construction limitations [63].

The site falls within roughness class II, typical of open agricultural land. A terrain exponent (α) of 0.14 is adopted for wind profile calculations.

Figure 4-3 presents the topographic and orographic characteristics of the site.

Figure 4-3 Topography and Orography Conditions of the Rimi Wind Farm

4.1.1.3 Location criteria

Proximity to infrastructure is essential for minimizing construction and operational costs. The site is located near existing access roads (Figure 4-4), reducing the need for new infrastructure development.

Additionally, the site is located approximately 500 m from the 330/132 kV Funtua substation (Figure 4-5), enabling efficient grid connection and reducing transmission losses.

Figure 4-4 Wind Farm Proximity to Assess Roads

Figure 4-5 Proximity to Electricity Grid

4.1.1.4 Climatology criteria

Wind resource availability is the most critical factor in wind farm development. The study area exhibits favourable wind conditions at multiple hub heights (10 m, 100 m, and 150 m).

Wind data used in this study were obtained from the Global Wind Atlas and NASA POWER datasets. A detailed description of data sources and validation is provided in Appendix C.

The generalized wind climate (GWC) used for simulation is shown in Figure 4-6.

Figure 4-6 Generalized Wind Climate (GWC) Data

4.1.2 Turbine selection

The energy output of a wind turbine is primarily governed by rotor swept area and wind speed, with energy capture increasing proportionally to the square of the rotor diameter. Based on these considerations, the General Electric GE 5.3 MW–158 wind turbine was selected for the Lamber Rimi expansion due to its large rotor diameter (158 m) and corresponding swept area of 19,607 m², which enables enhanced energy capture at moderate wind regimes. Although the turbine entails higher capital expenditure, this is offset by reduced balance-of-system costs, as installation, commissioning, and operational expenses are largely independent of turbine size. The turbine’s proven deployment in established wind markets and GE’s extensive operational experience in Sub-Saharan Africa further support its suitability for the project [62, 63, 64].

Energy production estimates were derived using turbine power curve data and site-specific wind speeds, with calculations implemented in Microsoft Excel rather than specialized wind modelling software such as WAsP.

4.1.3 Turbine siting

A central challenge in wind farm planning is mitigating the wake effect, where an upwind turbine creates a region of slowed and turbulent air that reduces the power output and increases the mechanical loads on downwind turbines [72] [67].

To maximize net energy yield, the farm layout must optimize turbine spacing, typically recommended at 3-5 rotor diameters (D) within a row and 5-9D between rows, aligned with the prevailing wind direction, as illustrated in Figure 4-7 [73].

Figure 4-7 Wind farm with optimum spacing

While specialized software like WAsP is typically used for this purpose, wake losses for this project were estimated using the widely recognized Jensen (Park) analytical wake model, implemented in Microsoft Excel. Assuming a thrust coefficient of 0.8, wake decay constant $k = 0.05$, and a sensitivity analysis was performed on inter-turbine spacings of 4D, 6D, and 8D (available on demand). The results, summarized

in Table 4-1, indicated that while 8D spacing minimized wake losses to 3.9%, the 6D spacing offered a favourable balance between land use efficiency and energy loss, with a calculated average wake loss of 5.4%. This 6D layout was therefore selected for the final design. The total farm AEP for 32 turbines is thus reduced from 573.4 GWh to 541.9 GWh. The wind farm energy yield report is summarized in Table 4-2

Table 4-1 Sensitivity on diameter spacing

Spacing	Average Power Ratio	Wake Loss (%)
4D	0.91	8.5
6D	0.95	5.4
8D	0.96	3.9

Table 4-2 Wind farm energy yield report

Parameter	Total	Average
Gross AEP (incl. wake losses) [GWh]	541.9	16.9
Gross AEP (excl. wake losses) [GWh]	573.4	17.9
Wake losses [%]	5.4	-

4.1.3.1 Energy yield and losses

Energy yield represents the net electrical power delivered to the grid, calculated as the gross energy generated by the wind turbines minus all systemic losses incurred during production ^[67]. Since this net yield is what is ultimately supplied to the electrical grid at the point of common coupling (PCC), it is essential to account for all technical and operational losses that occur between the turbine rotors and the PCC. These various losses are itemized in Table 4-3.

Table 4-3 Additional technical losses applicable for wind farm siting

Technical loss type	Typical	Typical	Range	Used	GWh/year
Availability	Turbine availability	> 3%			
	Balance of plant availability	< 1%	2-10%	4%	21.676
	Grid availability	< 1%			
Electrical	Operational electrical losses	1-2%	2-3%	2%	10.838
	Wind farm consumption				
Turbine Performance	Power curve adjustments	1-2%	0-5%	2%	10.838
	High wind hysteresis				
	Control losses (SCADA)				
Environmental	Blade degradation and fouling	1-2%	1-6%	2%	10.838
	Degradation due to icing				
	High and low temperature				
Curtailments	Wind sector management	Design dependent	0-5%	2%	10.838
	Grid curtailment				
	Noise, visual and environment				
Total Losses					65.028

All identified losses are quantified on a site-specific basis and deducted from the gross Annual Energy Production (AEP) to arrive at the net AEP, also termed the P₅₀ value. Statistically, this P₅₀ value indicates that the actual annual energy production is expected to be exceeded 50% of the time [75].

Beyond these operational and technical losses, it is also critical to consider the uncertainties. This includes the tool's sensitivity to variations in input data and parameters, which directly impacts the accuracy of the energy yield assessment. For onshore wind farms in Europe, the aggregate uncertainty in yield estimation typically ranges between 10% and 15% of the AEP; for this thesis, a value of 10% will be assumed [75].

Furthermore, the industry often prefers to use P₇₅ or P₉₀ AEP values for project planning and financing. These metrics indicate a higher probability of exceedance (75% and 90%, respectively), making them more conservative and attractive to investors and lenders [74]. The P₉₀ AEP value presented in Table 4-4 was calculated based on a Gaussian normal distribution.

Table 4-4 Energy Yield calculation

ID	Data	Value
1	Gross AEP P ₅₀ (incl. wake losses)	541.9 GWh
2	Total losses	65.028 GWh
3	Net AEP P ₅₀ = (1-2)	476.87 GWh
4	Uncertainty	10%
5	Net AEP P ₉₀	415.83 GWh
6	Capacity Factor	28%

The performance of the wind farm is evaluated using the capacity factor (Cp), a metric that quantifies the actual energy output against its maximum potential output if it operated at full rated power continuously.

For this project, the calculated capacity factor is 28%. This result is below the global weighted-average capacity factor for onshore wind, which is approximately 36% [75]. The discrepancy can be attributed to site-specific conditions such as local wind patterns, turbine array losses from the wake effect, and other operational efficiencies that differ from the global average

4.2 Wind Farm Economic Viability and Analysis

For decarbonization efforts to be effective, renewable energy projects must demonstrate not only technical feasibility but also economic viability. Sound policies, coupled with strong economic performance, are essential to spur sectorial growth and attract investment from private entities and financial institutions [76]. Therefore, a comprehensive economic assessment is a prerequisite for any investment decision in a wind power project.

4.2.1 Wind Farm Structure

The installation of the wind turbine itself constitutes the single largest capital expenditure over a wind farm's lifecycle. The total installed cost can be categorized into four primary components, as detailed in Figure 4-8. The wind turbine generator is the most significant, accounting for approximately 64-68% of the total cost [77]. Other major categories include grid connection (9-11%) and civil works, such as foundations (around 16%). Planning and miscellaneous expenses typically represent the remaining 9%.

Figure 4-8 Typical Onshore wind farm installed cost breakdown ^[6]

In practice, the installation cost per kilowatt varies significantly across regions and is influenced by turbine specifications and site-specific factors. These include turbine yield, transportation logistics, local content policies, land-use constraints, and labour rates. According to IRENA's 2019 report, the weighted average installation cost for onshore wind projects in Africa was 1,952 US\$/kW. The same report indicates that the lowest 5% of projects had costs at or below 1,448 USD/kW, while the highest 5% were at or above 2,189 US\$/kW ^[6]. For this thesis, a total installed cost or CAPEX of 1,800 US\$/kW will be assumed.

4.2.2 Economic Analysis Framework

Economic analysis involves forecasting project-related costs and revenues and evaluating financial viability using standard indicators such as the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), Net Present Value (NPV), and Internal Rate of Return (IRR) ^[33]. The analysis in this study is conducted over a project lifetime of 20 years.

The detailed mathematical formulations are provided in Appendix B, while a summary of the key input parameters is presented in Table 4-5. The overall project cash flow and financial performance are illustrated in Figure 4-9.

Table 4-5 Summary of Key Economic Inputs and Results

Category	Parameter	Value	Unit
Technical	Annual Energy Production	415,808,297.63	kWh/year
	Project Lifetime	20	years
	Number of Turbines	32	-
	Turbine Cost (per unit)	9,540,000	USD
	Total CAPEX	305,280,000	USD
Financing	Debt Share	85	%
	Equity Share	15	%
	Loan Amount	259,488,000	USD
	Equity Investment	45,792,000	USD
	Interest	5	%
	Discount Rate	6.5	%
	Loan Term	20	years
Operational	O&M Cost (annual)	7,632,000	USD/year
	Electricity Price	0.085	USD/kWh
	Annual Revenue	35,343,705.30	USD/year
	Annual Expenditure	28,453,988.46	USD/year
Results	Present Value of Energy	4,581,586,740.90	kWh
	Present Value of Cost	389,373,247.31	USD
	LCOE	0.085	USD/kWh

4.2.2.1 Cash Flow Analysis

Investment decisions require a detailed year-by-year assessment of project financial performance. In this study, a Cash Flow Model (CFM) was developed in Microsoft Excel to evaluate the economic viability of the proposed wind farm.

The model estimates annual revenues, operating costs, and financing obligations over the project lifetime to determine the net cash flow. All cash flows are discounted using a discount rate of 6.5% to account for the time value of money (Table 4-6).

This approach enables the evaluation of key financial indicators, including Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), and Debt-Service Coverage Ratio (DSCR).

It should be noted that the results of the cash flow analysis depend on assumptions regarding future revenues, costs, and financial conditions, which may vary due to

market uncertainties [89]. A graphical representation of the project cash flow over the 20-year lifetime is presented in Figure 4-9.

Figure 4-9 The Cash Flow of the wind farm (170 MW)

Table 4-6 Inputs and Outputs of the cash flow model

Category	Parameter	Value	Unit
Input	Electricity price	0.085	USD/kWh
	Equity investment	45,792,000.00	USD
	Annual revenue	35,343,705.30	USD/year
	Annual expenditure (O&M + Loan Servicing)	28,453,988.46	USD/year
	Net cash flow	6.889,716.83	USD/year
	Discount Rate	6.5	%
Output	Discounting Factor	11.02	-
	Net Present Value (NPV)	28,167,113.69	USD
	Return on Equity (IRR)	15.05	%

4.3 Policy and Regulatory Framework Analysis

Building upon the established technical and economic feasibility of the Lambar Rimi wind farm, this section addresses the critical third dimension of project viability: the policy and regulatory landscape. A wind energy project's success is contingent not only on robust resources and sound economics but also on a supportive and predictable legal environment. This analysis therefore examines Nigeria's existing renewable energy policy framework, benchmarks it against the internationally proven German Bürgerwindpark model, and identifies the specific gaps that must

be bridged to translate the techno-economic potential demonstrated in the previous sections into tangible, bankable projects.

4.3.1 The Nigerian Renewable Energy Policy Landscape

Nigeria’s commitment to renewable energy development is reflected in several key policy frameworks. The National Energy Policy (2003) established the foundation for integrating renewable energy into the national energy mix. This was followed by the Renewable Energy Master Plan (2005), which set measurable targets for increasing renewable electricity generation. The National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (2015) further strengthened this framework by promoting renewable integration and energy efficiency. Most recently, the Energy Transition Plan (2022) outlines Nigeria’s pathway toward net-zero emissions by 2060, positioning renewable energy as a central component of the transition ^{[91] [92] [14] [93]}.

These successive frameworks demonstrate a consistent progression in national priorities, from target-setting to implementation enablers, as summarized in Table 4-7 below, which outlines key renewable energy policy milestones from 2003 to 2022.

Table 4-7 Policy Evolution in Nigeria's Renewable Energy Sector

Year	Policy/Document	Issuing Body
¹⁴ 2003	National Energy Policy (NEP)	Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN)
¹⁵ 2005	Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP)	Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN)
¹⁶ 2015	National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP)	Federal Ministry of Power
¹⁷ 2022	Energy Transition Plan (ETP)	Federal Government of Nigeria

¹⁴ Promote sustainable energy resources, including solar for rural electrification, foundational for renewables integration

¹⁵ Increase renewable electricity share to 23% by 2025 and 36% by 2030; specific capacities: 2 GW small hydro, 500 MW solar PV, 400 MW biomass, 40 MW wind by 2025.

¹⁶ Enable renewable deployment via incentives; mainstream energy efficiency; support off-grid solutions for 10% total energy from renewables by 2025.

¹⁷ Achieve net-zero by 2060; 30 GW renewable capacity by 2030 (including up to 5 GW solar focus, with wind potential exploration); \$1.9 trillion investment pathway.

Despite these policy developments, the implementation record remains weak. Nigeria's installed wind-power capacity currently stands at less than 15 MW, primarily from pilot-scale Katsina Wind Farm, with smaller installations in Lagos, and Sokoto ^[95]. This figure represents less than 0.01 % of the total national generation mix, highlighting the persistent gap between strategic intent and operational realization.

A major weakness of the policy framework is its lack of technology specificity. While targets for renewable-energy penetration are well defined, operational focus and financial incentives have been disproportionately directed toward solar energy. The absence of dedicated procurement mechanisms, feed-in tariffs, or integration roadmaps for wind has discouraged investors and limited the emergence of a viable project pipeline ^[22] ^[7].

Furthermore, Nigeria's regulatory environment, supervised by the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) remains cumbersome and multi-layered. Independent Power Producers (IPPs) face lengthy procedures for licensing, environmental approvals, and land acquisition that involve overlapping jurisdictions between federal and state agencies ^[95] ^[96]. This complexity amplifies project-development risk and transaction costs, deterring both domestic and foreign investment.

Beyond the policy domain, physical infrastructure constitutes an additional constraint. The national transmission grid is chronically underdeveloped and not geographically aligned with renewable resource potential. High-wind zones identified in the northern corridor remain severely grid-constrained, preventing evacuation of potential generation and undermining the business case for investment ^[91]. This misalignment forces the need for integrated resource-to-grid planning that strategically links wind potential zones with transmission expansion priorities (Figure 4-10).

Figure 4-10 Existing and Planned Transmission Network of the Nigerian Grid

4.3.2 International Best Practice: The German Bürgerwindpark (Citizen Wind Farm) Model

Germany’s Energiewende (energy transition) has become a global reference point for the successful integration of renewable energy, particularly onshore wind into national energy systems. Central to this achievement is the Bürgerwindpark (citizen windfarm) model, which at its peak accounted for nearly half of Germany’s installed wind capacity (BMWK, 2023). This approach is underpinned by a synergistic framework of three interlocking pillars that transform local citizens from passive observers into active investors and beneficiaries, as illustrated in Figure 4-11.

Figure 4-11 Conceptual Overview of the Bürgerwindpark

The Bürgerwindpark model is built on citizen ownership, participatory planning, and professional management, combining local investment, social acceptance, and technical reliability to support sustainable wind energy development^{[96] [97] [98][99]}.

Collectively, these pillars create a self-reinforcing ecosystem in which project success aligns with community welfare. The contrast with Nigeria’s top-down, government-centric development model is striking. Germany’s decentralized citizen-ownership structure inherently builds trust, diversifies capital sources, and embeds social sustainability into project lifecycles.

4.3.3 Analysis and Identification of Actionable Policy Gaps

Benchmarking Nigeria’s policy framework against Germany’s Bürgerwindpark model reveals several systemic, actionable gaps. The comparison (Figure 4-12) below summarizes these across key development domains.

Figure 4-12 Comparative framework of wind energy policy in Germany and Nigeria, highlighting differences in financial mechanisms, community participation, grid integration, permitting processes, and policy continuity.

4.4 A Framework for the Adaptation of a Community Based Wind Energy Model in Nigeria

4.4.1 Conceptual Foundation and Rationale for Adaptation

This section proposes a structured framework for the implementation of community-owned wind energy projects in Nigeria, drawing upon the established principles of Germany's Bürgerwindpark (citizen wind farm) model. The German case study has demonstrated significant efficacy in decentralizing energy assets, leveraging community ownership, participatory governance, and local benefit-sharing to deploy over 10 GW of capacity through citizen-led initiatives [21].

However, the direct implementation of this model in Nigeria is not viable without significant contextual modification. This framework, therefore, proposes a systematic adaptation of its core tenets to align with the distinct socio-economic, institutional, and cultural dynamics of Nigeria. The objective is to secure essential community buy in. This is a critical success factor in a context characterized by historical land use conflicts and scepticism toward external developers [23] and to provide a viable pathway toward achieving national energy access and decarbonization goals.

4.4.2 Adaptation Methodology

The adaptation methodology involves the recalibration of the core Bürgerwindpark principles to suit local conditions. Figure 4-13 provides a comparative analysis of the original principles and their proposed Nigerian adaptations

Figure 4-13 Conceptual framework illustrating the adaptation of Bürgerwindpark principles from Germany to the Nigerian context through governance, financing, regulatory, and benefit distribution mechanisms.

4.4.3 Phased Implementation Framework

The project is implemented in four sequential phases including initiation and community mobilization, feasibility and structuring, implementation and financial closure, and long term operation and benefit distribution. Each phase builds on the previous one, ensuring a structured transition from project conception to sustainable operation. The detailed activities and interdependencies are illustrated in Figure 4-14.

Figure 4-14 Phased Implementation Framework

4.4.4 Essential Government Enablers

The scalability of this framework beyond pilot projects depends on supportive government intervention. Key enabling factors include the formal integration of the community wind model into national policy frameworks such as the NREEEP and the Energy Transition Plan, providing strategic direction and legitimacy. In addition, regulatory streamlining is required to reduce procedural barriers, particularly through the introduction of fast-track licensing processes for small-scale projects, which would address current delays in approval timelines.

Financial support mechanisms are also essential to de-risk investment, including fiscal incentives and grant funding for feasibility studies through agencies such as the REA.

A phased implementation roadmap for these measures is presented in a Gantt-style chart, illustrating the timeline for effective deployment (Figure 4-15).

Figure 4-15 Phased Implementation Roadmap for the Nigerian Community Wind Model

5 Results & Discussion

This chapter presents and interprets the results obtained from the GIS-based wind resource assessment, techno-economic modelling, and policy analysis. It discusses these findings in relation to the study's research questions and objectives, providing insights into the feasibility, challenges, and opportunities for onshore wind energy deployment in Nigeria. The chapter concludes with a synopsis summarizing how the research questions have been addressed.

5.1 National Wind Resource Potential and Suitability Zoning

The national-scale GIS-based Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) provides a spatially explicit assessment of onshore wind energy suitability across Nigeria. By integrating wind resource characteristics, terrain constraints, and population-related limitations, the analysis produces a composite suitability index that reflects both technical feasibility and socio-environmental considerations. All criteria were standardized, weighted, and combined using a weighted linear summation approach within QGIS to generate the final suitability map (Figure 5-1).

The resulting suitability map was classified into five categories: Very High, High, Moderate, Low, and Very Low suitability. The spatial distribution of these classes reveals a clear north–south gradient in wind energy potential. Regions of Very High suitability are predominantly concentrated in the northwestern and northeastern parts of Nigeria, where strong and consistent wind regimes coincide with low surface roughness, gentle terrain, and relatively low population density. These conditions are particularly favourable for utility-scale wind farm development.

High suitability zones extend across parts of the northern and north-central regions, where wind speeds remain adequate and terrain conditions are generally favourable, though localized constraints such as moderate slopes or increasing population density slightly reduce overall suitability. These areas remain viable for large-scale or clustered wind energy projects.

Moderate suitability zones are primarily located within the central belt of Nigeria. Although wind speeds are comparatively lower, these regions may still support medium-scale wind installations or hybrid renewable energy systems, especially where proximity to existing infrastructure offsets reduced wind potential.

In contrast, Low and Very Low suitability zones dominate much of southern Nigeria. These regions are characterized by lower wind speeds, higher surface roughness, and dense settlement patterns, which collectively limit the feasibility of utility-

scale wind development. While large wind farms are unlikely in these areas, localized applications such as micro-wind systems or hybrid solar–wind solutions may still be feasible in specific contexts.

Overall, the MCDA results indicate that approximately 45% of Nigeria’s land area falls within the High to Very High suitability categories, highlighting the strategic importance of the northern corridor for onshore wind deployment. These findings fulfil Research Objective 1 by identifying priority regions for wind energy development while establishing a robust spatial framework for subsequent techno-economic analysis.

Spatial Classification of Wind Resources and Potential in Nigeria

Figure 5-1 National Onshore Wind Energy Suitability Map of Nigeria (MCDA Result).

Table 5-1 Summary of MCDA-Based Wind Energy Suitability Classes in Nigeria.

Suitability Class	Dominant Characteristics	Approximate Land Area (%)
¹⁸ Very High	High wind speed, low roughness, gentle slope, low population density	26.3
¹⁹ High	Adequate wind regime, favourable terrain, moderate population density	19.5
²⁰ Moderate	Moderate wind speeds, mixed terrain constraints	26.5
²¹ Low	Low wind speeds, higher roughness, increasing settlement density	16.36
²² Very Low	Poor wind regime, dense settlements, land-use conflicts	11.38

5.2 Techno-Economic Feasibility of the Lambar Rimi Case Study

Building upon the national wind resource assessment, a detailed techno-economic analysis was performed for the Lambar Rimi Wind Farm in Katsina State, located in north-western Nigeria. The site lies within the very high suitability zone identified by the GIS–MCDA and represents an ideal benchmark for evaluating the technical and financial feasibility of large-scale onshore wind projects in the region.

5.2.1 Wind Resource Characterisation

Hourly wind speed data for the year 2024 were obtained from the NASA POWER Reanalysis Database for the Lambar Rimi coordinates (12.85° N, 7.71° E) at a reference height of 10 m. The dataset was processed in Microsoft Excel and Python to eliminate outliers, compute statistical parameters, and evaluate monthly and annual profiles. Due to the modern trend toward taller turbine configurations, the data were extrapolated to a 150 m hub height using the exponential wind-profile equation with a height exponent of 0.14 m, representative of semi-arid terrain. The full hourly dataset are available upon request.

¹⁸ Highly suitable for utility-scale wind farms

¹⁹ Suitable for large-scale wind development with minor constraints

²⁰ Conditionally suitable for medium-scale or hybrid systems

²¹ Limited suitability for grid-connected wind

²² Unsuitable for utility-scale wind development

The extrapolation increased the mean annual wind speed from 6.2 m/s at 10 m to 8.02 m/s at 150 m, confirming the strong influence of height on wind energy potential in inland sites. Monthly averages were computed to reveal temporal variability throughout the year. As illustrated in Figure 5-2 a., wind speeds were clearly above 7 m/s peak between mid-November and early March, corresponding to the Harmattan season, and decline between June and September during the wet monsoon period. This pattern forms the characteristic bathtub profile Figure 5-2 b., signifying high energy availability during the dry months and reduced intensity mid-year. Such complementarity with solar radiation suggests strong potential for wind–solar hybridization, enhancing year-round generation stability. Detailed monthly wind-speed graphs for January–December 2024 are available upon request.

Figure 5-2 (a) Daily variation of wind speed at 150 m and (b) monthly average wind speed showing a bathtub profile over the study period.

5.2.2 Statistical Analysis of the Wind Regime

To quantify the statistical behaviour of the site’s wind resource, a Weibull probability distribution was fitted to the hourly dataset. The resulting parameters were a shape factor (k) of 3.1 and a scale factor (c) of 8.8 m/s, indicating a stable, medium-wind regime well suited for utility-scale development (Figure 5-3). The probability density function (PDF) and cumulative frequency curve are shown in Figure 5-4, while the annual duration curve in demonstrates that wind speeds exceed 6 m/s for approximately 68 % of the year. This ensures consistent turbine operation and supports an estimated capacity factor of about 28 % for the proposed installation.

Figure 5-3 Weibull probability distribution fit

Figure 5-4 Probability Density Function and Cumulative Density Function chart

Figure 5-5 Annual and Hourly duration curve

The results align closely with other empirical assessments in northern Nigeria [22, 74], reinforcing the reliability of the Lambar Rimi site as a prototype for scaling up wind deployment nationwide.

5.2.3 Energy Yield Estimation

Using the GE 5.3-158 turbine (158 m rotor, 150 m hub height), the projected Net Annual Energy Production (AEP P_{50}) for a 170 MW plant comprising 32 turbines is 476.87 GWh/year. Incorporating a 10 % uncertainty factor yields a conservative P_{90} value of 415.83 GWh, reflecting potential inter-annual variability. The corresponding capacity factor of 28 % compares favourably with the early-stage wind markets of sub-Saharan Africa and demonstrates promising generation potential under local meteorological conditions.

Wake and electrical losses were estimated at 5.4% and 2.0%, respectively, while planned maintenance downtime accounted for an additional 2% energy loss. These realistic assumptions form the basis of the financial modelling used.

5.2.4 Financial Feasibility Analysis

The economic evaluation employed a discounted cash-flow approach over a 20-year operational life. The main assumptions included:

1. CAPEX: US\$ 1,800 per kW
2. O & M: 2.5% of the CAPEX
3. Discount Rate: 6.5%
4. Equity-Debt ratio: 15: 85
5. Electricity tariff: US\$ 0.085 per kWh

Under these parameters, the calculated Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) is US\$ 0.085 per kWh, competitive with Nigeria's existing generation mix and comparable to the solar IPP tariff benchmark of US\$ 0.075 per kWh. The model yields a Net Present Value (NPV) of US\$ 28.2 million and an Internal Rate of Return (IRR) of 15.05 %, substantially exceeding the applied discount rate. The simple payback period is approximately 10 years, suggesting cost recovery within half the project's lifespan. The complete cash-flow sheet is available upon request.

5.3 Policy Benchmarking and Community Wind Model Adaptation

While the preceding analyses demonstrate that Nigeria possesses both the technical resource base and economic justification for wind energy investment, the sector re-

mains largely undeveloped. This issue stems from institutional, regulatory, and social challenges that have hindered implementation. Benchmarking against international best practices, specifically Germany's Bürgerwindpark (Citizen Wind Farm) model provides a useful lens for identifying policy gaps and contextual adaptation strategies.

Germany's success in deploying community-based wind projects lies in its integrated framework combining three fundamental pillars: citizen ownership and financing, participatory planning, and professional project management. This model is supported by consistent policy mechanisms such as technology-specific feed-in tariffs, cooperative investment structures (e.g., GmbH & Co. KG and eG models), and transparent permitting procedures. At its peak, community-owned projects accounted for nearly half of Germany's onshore wind capacity, demonstrating that decentralization and profitability can coexist.

By contrast, Nigeria's current renewable energy policy environment guided by the National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy [83] and the Energy Transition Plan [14] lacks a targeted mechanism for wind energy. Incentives are largely solar-centric, and project licensing remains multi-layered and time-consuming, involving approvals from the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC), the Federal Ministry of Environment, and state authorities. Furthermore, the absence of community participation frameworks has limited public trust and contributed to social resistance in some renewable projects.

To address these deficiencies, this research proposes an Adapted Community Wind Framework for Nigeria, which retains the structural logic of the Bürgerwindpark but redefines it for local conditions. The model emphasizes the role of traditional institutions and local leaders as project champions, fostering trust in high-context communities where formal cooperatives are less common. Financing structures would blend community equity contributions with development finance from institutions such as the Bank of Industry (BOI), the African Development Bank (AfDB), and the Green Climate Fund (GCF), thereby mitigating capital constraints.

A phased implementation plan is recommended, beginning with pilot projects below 20 MW to test governance models, streamline permitting, and establish operational credibility. Over time, these could scale into regional clusters of community-owned wind farms integrated with the national grid. This framework directly addresses Research Objective 3, providing a feasible pathway to align Nigeria's policy ambitions with ground-level implementation.

5.4 Integrated Discussion: Barriers and Opportunities

Synthesizing the technical, economic, and policy results presents a holistic understanding of the enablers and constraints shaping wind energy development in Nigeria. The analyses demonstrate that, although the northern corridor exhibits strong technical potential and favourable project economics, achieving large-scale deployment requires an integrated strategy that combines infrastructure reinforcement, policy innovation, and technological hybridization with solar energy (Figure 5-6, Figure 5-7).

5.4.1 Infrastructural and Regulatory Barriers

A critical constraint to wind energy expansion lies in the infrastructural asymmetry between high-resource zones and the existing power network. The northern states of Katsina, Sokoto, and Jigawa, identified as the most suitable for large-scale wind generation, coincide with regions of limited grid capacity and aging transmission assets. Without synchronized grid expansion under the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN), these areas risk producing stranded generation potential projects that generate energy but cannot deliver it efficiently to demand centres.

Regulatory processes further compound this challenge. Under the current framework, Independent Power Producers (IPPs) must navigate multi-agency licensing involving NERC, state governments, and environmental authorities. This fragmented permitting structure results in extended timelines and high transaction costs. Moreover, the absence of wind-specific procurement mechanisms such as feed-in tariffs, reverse auctions, or dedicated PPA templates creates uncertainty for investors and lenders, weakening Nigeria's competitiveness against regional markets like Kenya or South Africa, where policy clarity has driven private-sector growth.

Figure 5-6 Barriers affecting the proposed wind farm

5.4.2 Security and Socio-Political Challenges

Beyond regulatory hurdles, the security situation in Northern Nigeria poses a significant operational and investment risk to renewable energy projects. The persistent threat of banditry, insurgency, and community-level conflicts in parts of Katsina, Zamfara, and Borno States introduces logistical constraints to site access, equipment transport, and long-term maintenance activities.

These risks elevate insurance premiums, inflate capital costs, and deter foreign investment despite favourable wind conditions. Project developers and financiers frequently classify northern regions as high-risk zones, limiting the availability of credit guarantees or concessional financing.

However, this challenge also emphasises on the need of community-based ownership models and local partnership structures, as discussed in Section 4.4. Empowering local communities through joint ownership, employment, and revenue-sharing reduces the likelihood of project vandalism and enhances social license. For example, collaboration with traditional rulers, local security committees, and vigilante networks can provide grassroots protection frameworks for wind farms in remote areas.

From a policy perspective, integrating security risk assessments into early-stage feasibility studies and offering risk mitigation instruments such as sovereign guarantees or security-related tax rebates would help de-risk investments in high-resource but fragile regions. This approach aligns with Nigeria's broader Energy Transition Implementation Plan, which emphasizes inclusive and regionally balanced renewable deployment.

Figure 5-7 Solutions to the barriers

5.4.3 Financial Constraints and Market Dynamics

The economic findings of this study demonstrate that a well-structured wind project, such as the Lambar Rimi 170 MW expansion, can achieve an LCOE of US\$ 0.085/kWh and an IRR of 15.05%, indicating strong financial viability. Yet, these metrics are highly sensitive to the cost of capital, which remains elevated due to investor risk perception and currency volatility.

Domestic banks typically offer short-term, high-interest loans unsuitable for infrastructure projects with 20-year lifespans. Development Finance Institutions (DFIs), such as the African Development Bank (AfDB) and the Green Climate Fund (GCF), provide longer-tenor options, but uptake remains limited due to the absence of clear government guarantees or power market reforms ensuring payment security.

The creation of blended finance mechanisms, combining local equity participation, concessional debt, and climate financing, would improve affordability and stimulate project pipelines. Similarly, integrating currency hedging instruments and import duty exemptions for turbine components could further enhance project bankability.

5.4.4 The Case for Hybrid Wind-Solar Systems

The temporal analysis in Section 5.2 revealed a distinct bathtub wind speed profile, with peak energy availability between November and March and reduced output during the monsoon months. This seasonal pattern complements solar photovoltaic (PV) generation, which is strongest between May and September. Consequently, hybrid wind–solar installations present a technically and economically viable strategy to mitigate intermittency, stabilize output, and optimize grid utilization.

Hybrid configurations offer multiple advantages for Nigeria's energy sector. The complementary nature of wind and solar generation ensures a smoother power output profile, which reduces intermittency and diminishes the requirement for large-scale, costly energy storage solutions. Furthermore, the sharing of critical infrastructure such as inverters, substations, and transmission lines leads to a significant reduction in overall capital expenditure (CAPEX). This configuration also enhances load balancing, thereby greatly improving the stability of mini grids, a critical factor for remote northern communities with weak or non-existent grid interconnections.

The application of hybrid systems spans multiple scales. At the utility level, large-scale hybrid parks that co-locate wind and solar capacity can function as anchor generation hubs. These hubs have the potential to power agricultural processing, irrigation systems, and emerging industrial clusters, thereby catalysing rural economic development. On a smaller scale, hybrid microgrids for instance, those combining 5 MW of wind with 10 MW of solar and battery storage can provide reliable,

clean electricity to off-grid towns in states like Sokoto or Yobe. This directly reduces dependency on diesel generators and associated emissions. To fully realize these opportunities, Nigeria's regulatory framework must be adapted to explicitly recognize and accommodate hybrid generation models. The Rural Electrification Agency (REA) could pioneer this transition through its Nigeria Electrification Project (NEP) by creating specific incentives for developers to design hybrid mini-grids and introducing performance-based grants for projects that successfully integrate wind and solar assets.

5.4.5 Social and Institutional Opportunities

The community wind framework proposed in Chapter 4 offers a strategic pathway to embed principles of social inclusion, local economic participation, and security resilience within Nigeria's energy transition. By enabling local stakeholders to participate in project financing and governance, communities transform from passive beneficiaries into active custodians of the energy infrastructure. This sense of ownership directly mitigates risks of vandalism and ensures long-term social license to operate.

However, the primary hurdle for implementing this model is the initial mobilization of capital and expertise for feasibility studies and project development. Local communities often lack the upfront resources for these critical first steps. To overcome this, the government or development partners could establish a pre-development grant fund, administered through agencies like the Rural Electrification Agency (REA) or the Bank of Industry (BOI), specifically targeted at community-led renewable energy initiatives. A successfully implemented pilot project would then serve as a tangible blueprint for replication across other northern states.

Realizing this potential necessitates robust institutional coordination. The Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC), the Rural Electrification Agency (REA), and the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN) must align their efforts. The development of a joint renewable infrastructure plan which synchronizes grid expansion with high-resolution resource mapping would optimize public investment and promote equitable regional development. Furthermore, the establishment of Renewable Energy Development Zones (REDZ), modelled on successful initiatives like those in South Africa, could create secure, designated clusters for hybrid energy projects. These zones would benefit from streamlined regulations, dedicated logistics corridors, and enhanced security provisions, thereby concentrating development efforts and mitigating operational risks.

5.4.6 Strategic Outlook

In conclusion, the northern corridor of Nigeria possesses a uniquely advantageous profile for renewable energy, characterized by high-density wind resources and

complementary solar irradiation. This positions the region as a foundational pillar for the nation's sustainable energy future. Capitalizing on this potential, however, demands a comprehensive and integrated strategy. This includes modernizing and expanding transmission infrastructure, de-risking capital deployment through blended finance models, and directly addressing socio-economic drivers of instability via inclusive, community-owned development frameworks.

Within this strategy, hybrid wind-solar systems emerge as the most technically and economically viable solution for delivering consistent, renewable power. Concurrently, models grounded in local ownership and participatory governance are identified as critical for ensuring social acceptance and long-term project sustainability. The deliberate integration of these technological and social approaches into the national Energy Transition Plan will yield benefits that transcend energy access, actively contributing to climate resilience, economic diversification, and peacebuilding in the northern regions.

5.5 Synopsis

Research question 1

Spatial Distribution of Wind Potential

The GIS-MCDA identified the northern states (Katsina, Sokoto, Jigawa, Zamfara, Borno) as the very high suitability zone, with mean wind speeds exceeding 7 m/s at 150m. Southern states have lower potential (about 4.5 m/s), suitable only for small-scale or hybrid systems.

Research question 2

Techno-Economic Performance

The Lambar Rimi case study (170 MW) confirms viability, with a projected LCOE of \$0.085/kWh, an IRR of 15.05%, and a capacity factor of 28%. These metrics are competitive with global benchmarks and other energy sources in Nigeria.

Research question 3

Required Policy Frameworks

Nigeria's policy landscape lacks wind-specific incentives and streamlined processes. An Adapted Community Wind Framework, based on the German Bürgerwindpark model but tailored to the Nigerian context, is proposed to enable development through blended finance and participatory governance.

Research Question 4

Barriers and Opportunities

Key barriers are grid constraints, regulatory complexity, high financing costs, and security concerns. Major opportunities lie in the resource complementarity with solar for hybrid systems, strong project economics, and the potential for community ownership to enhance social acceptance.

Research Question 5

Integrated Framework for Transition

The integration of geospatial analysis, techno-economic modelling, and policy benchmarking demonstrates that a strategy focused on hybrid wind-solar systems and community-based models is the most viable pathway to unlock Nigeria's estimated 3.2 GW of wind potential and accelerate its energy transition.

6 Conclusion

This research has systematically established that onshore wind energy constitutes a viable and strategic asset for achieving a sustainable and secure energy future in Nigeria. The integrated application of Geographic Information Systems, techno-economic modelling, and policy benchmarking has yielded a holistic assessment, connecting physical potential with practical implementation frameworks. The investigation confirms that Nigeria possesses significant untapped wind resources, primarily concentrated in the northern geographical corridor. States such as Katsina, Sokoto, and Jigawa emerged as high-priority zones, exhibiting wind speeds and land characteristics that are highly conducive to utility-scale wind farm development.

The financial analysis conducted for a representative project at Lambar Rimi demonstrated clear economic feasibility, with an energy cost that is competitive within the current power market. This finding underscores the potential for wind energy to attract investment and contribute meaningfully to the national grid. A critical outcome of the policy review was the identification of a regulatory gap concerning community-centric renewable energy models. In response, this thesis proposed an Adapted Community Wind Framework, which translates the core principles of successful international models into a structure suited to Nigeria's socio-economic context. This framework prioritizes local ownership, blended financing, and participatory governance to ensure that energy development also fosters social equity and local economic development.

Furthermore, the study concluded that the integration of wind and solar power into hybrid systems represents a technically and economically superior pathway for the northern regions. This approach mitigates the intermittency of each individual resource, enhances grid stability, and provides a more reliable source of clean electricity. Collectively, these findings indicate that with targeted policy support and strategic investment, wind energy can be a major contributor to Nigeria's national goals for renewable energy generation and carbon emission reduction.

6.1 Critical Reflection

During this investigation, several limitations were encountered which merit acknowledgment. The primary constraint pertained to the resolution of wind resource data. The reliance on global reanalysis datasets, while valuable for a national-scale assessment, introduces a degree of uncertainty at specific project sites. Future developments would benefit greatly from high-fidelity, localized wind measurements.

Additionally, the techno-economic models were built upon a set of financial assumptions, including static costs and exchange rates. The dynamic nature of Nigeria's economy means that factors such as inflation, currency fluctuation, and changes in import duties could alter project economics and would require dynamic modelling in future, more granular studies. The research also addressed the challenge of regional insecurity in a qualitative manner. A quantitative analysis of security-related costs and risks would provide a more robust foundation for investment decisions in affected areas.

Finally, while the proposed Adapted Community Wind Framework is grounded in rigorous policy benchmarking, it remains a conceptual model. Its ultimate efficacy and practicality depend on real-world implementation, which is beyond the scope of this desktop study and presents a fertile area for future applied research.

6.2 Recommendations for Future Research

To build upon the findings and address the limitations identified in this study, the following targeted research initiatives are proposed. These recommendations are designed to translate the conceptual framework and national-level assessment into actionable, ground-truthed strategies for development.

1. High-Resolution Wind Resource Assessment and Validation

A critical and immediate priority is the validation of wind resource data through empirical measurement campaigns. This requires the deployment of met masts or LiDAR technology for a minimum of 24 months within the high-potential zones identified in the northern corridor. The resulting high-fidelity data will serve to calibrate existing models, reduce investment uncertainty, and enable precise micro-siting and turbine selection for prospective projects.

2. Techno-Economic Optimization of Hybrid Energy Systems

Future work should focus on detailed modelling and simulation of integrated hybrid renewable systems. Utilizing specialized software tools such as HOMER Pro, PVSyst, or SAM, research should determine the optimal configuration of wind, solar, and battery storage to maximize dispatchability, ensure grid stability, and minimize the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) under Nigerian climatic conditions.

3. Dynamic Financial and Risk Modelling

To enhance investment readiness, subsequent financial analyses must incorporate dynamic risk variables. This involves employing probabilistic methods, such as Monte Carlo simulations, to model the impact of currency volatility, inflation, and fluctuating turbine import costs. Furthermore, interdisciplinary research with security experts is needed to quantify the financial impact of regional instability, leading

to the development of risk-adjusted financial models and tailored insurance products for the renewable energy sector.

4. Implementation and Impact Analysis of the Community Ownership Framework

The proposed Adapted Community Wind Framework requires empirical validation through pilot projects. Action research in selected communities should be conducted to evaluate the model's governance structures, benefit-sharing mechanisms, and socio-economic impacts. These case studies will provide critical evidence for refining the framework and scaling it effectively.

5. Policy Implementation and Regulatory Effectiveness Analysis

With the enactment of the Electricity Act 2023, ongoing policy research is essential. Studies should monitor the implementation of decentralized licensing and state-level energy policies, evaluating their effectiveness in reducing approval timelines and stimulating private investment in community-scale and utility-scale renewable projects.

6. Environmental and Land-Use Impact Studies

Prior to large-scale deployment, comprehensive environmental and social assessments are necessary. Research should investigate the potential ecological and land-use implications of wind farms in Nigeria's semi-arid and Savanna regions, ensuring that development aligns with principles of sustainable land management and biodiversity conservation.

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Appendix A. Fundamental Wind Energy Theory and Equations

A-1 Power Available in the Wind

The kinetic energy of a stream of air with mass m and moving with a velocity V is given by

$$E = \frac{1}{2}mV^2 \quad (1)$$

Consider a wind rotor of cross-sectional area A exposed to this wind stream as shown in Figure 2-1. The kinetic energy of the air stream available for the turbine can be expressed as

$$E = \frac{1}{2}\rho_a vV^2 \quad (2)$$

where ρ_a is the density of air and v is the volume of air parcel available to the rotor. The air parcel interacting with the rotor per unit time has a cross-sectional area equal to that of the rotor (A_T) and thickness equal to the wind velocity (V). Hence energy per unit time, that is power, can be expressed as

$$P = \frac{1}{2}\rho_a A_T V^3 \quad (3)$$

From equation 6, we can see that the factors influencing the power available in the wind stream are the air density, area of the wind rotor and the wind velocity. The effect of the wind velocity is more prominent owing to its cubic relationship with power.

A-2 Air Density Modelling

Factors like temperature, atmospheric pressure, elevation and air constituents affect the density of air. Dry air can be considered as an ideal gas. According to the ideal gas law,

$$pV_G = nRT \quad (4)$$

where p is the pressure, V_G is the volume of the gas, n is the number of kilo moles of the gas, R is the universal gas constant and T is the temperature. Density of air, which is the ratio of the mass of 1 kilo mole of air to its volume, is given by

$$\rho_a = \frac{m}{V_G} \quad (5)$$

From equation 7, density is given by

$$\rho_a = \frac{mP}{RT} \quad (6)$$

If we know the elevation Z and temperature T at a site, the air density can be calculated by

$$\rho_a = \frac{353.049}{T} e^{(-0.034 \frac{Z}{T})} \quad (7)$$

The density of air decreases with increase in site elevation and temperature. The air density may be taken as 1.225 for most of the practical cases. Due to this relatively low density, wind is rather a diffuse source of energy. Hence large sized systems are often required for substantial power production [30].

Aside from the wind speed, factors which influences wind flow include local wind effects, wind shear, roughness height, turbulence, acceleration effect and time variation [27], [24], [36]. The rate at which the velocity increases with height depends on the roughness of the terrain. Presence of dense vegetation like plantations, forests and bushes slows down the wind considerably. Level and smooth terrains do not have much effect on the wind speed [27]. The surface roughness terrain is usually represented by the roughness class or roughness height. It might be close to zero (surface of the sea) or even as high as 2 (town centres). Some typical values are 0.005 for flat and smooth terrains, 0.025 – 0.1 for open grass lands, 0.2 – 0.3 for row crops, 0.5 – 1 for orchards and shrubs and 1 – 2 for forests, town centres etc [27]. Speed and direction of wind change rapidly while it passes through surfaces and obstructions like buildings, trees and rocks. This is due to the turbulence generated in the flow. Figure 6-1 shows the presence of turbulence and how it reduces power available in the stream and imposes fatigue loads on the turbine.

Figure 6-1 Turbulence created by an obstruction [27]

A smooth ridge, as shown in Figure 6-2, accelerates the wind stream passing over it. The acceleration is caused by the squeezing of wind layers over the mount as shown in the figure. Hence mountain passes are geographical features causing acceleration of wind. A pass between two high hills, oriented parallel to the wind direction, would be a cleverly chosen site for wind turbines.

Figure 6-2 The acceleration effect over ridges ^[36]

A-3 Wind Turbine Power, Thrust, and Torque

Theoretical power available in a wind stream is given by equation 6 ^[29]. However, a turbine cannot extract this power completely from the wind. When the wind stream passes the turbine, a part of its kinetic energy is transferred to the rotor and the air leaving the turbine carries the rest away ^[29]. Actual power produced by a rotor would then be decided by the efficiency with which this energy transfer from wind to the rotor takes place. This efficiency is usually termed as the power coefficient (C_p). Thus, the power coefficient of the rotor can be defined as the ratio of actual power developed by the rotor to the theoretical power available in the wind.

Hence,

$$C_p = \frac{2P_T}{\rho_a A_T V^3} \quad (8)$$

where P_T is the power developed by the turbine. The power coefficient of a turbine depends on many factors such as the profile of the rotor blades, blade arrangement and setting etc. A designer would try to fix these parameters at its optimum level to attain maximum C_p at a wide range of wind velocities ^[29].

The thrust force experienced by the rotor (F) can be expressed as

$$F = \frac{1}{2} \rho_a A_T V^2 \quad (9)$$

Hence, we can represent the rotor torque (T) as

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \rho_a A_T V^2 \quad (10)$$

where R is the radius of the rotor. This is the maximum theoretical torque and in practice the rotor shaft can develop only a fraction of this maximum limit.

A-4 Wind Regime Analysis

The average wind speed (V_m) is given by

$$V_m = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n V_i \quad (11)$$

where V_i is the wind velocity and n is the number of wind data.

However, for wind power calculations, the equation is remodified for accuracy and its new form is

$$V_m = \left(\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n V_i^3 \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (12)$$

The weighted average expressed by equation 15 should be used in wind energy analysis [76].

Distribution of wind velocity

The standard deviation (σ_v) tells us the deviation of individual velocities from the mean value. Thus

$$\sigma_v = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (V_i - V_m)^2}{n}} \quad (13)$$

Lower values of σ_v indicate the uniformity of the data set [31].

A-5 Statistical models for wind data analysis

The Weibull and Rayleigh distributions can be used to describe the wind variations in a regime with an acceptable accuracy level. In the above distributions, the variations in wind velocity are characterized by two functions:

1. The probability density function
2. The cumulative density function.

The probability density function $f(V)$ indicates the fraction of time for which the wind is at a given velocity V. It is given by

$$f(V) = \frac{k}{A} \left(\frac{V}{A} \right)^{k-1} e^{-\left(\frac{V}{A} \right)^k} \quad (14)$$

Here, k is the Weibull shape factor and A is the scale factor [25].

The cumulative distribution of the velocity V gives us the fraction of time (or probability) that the wind velocity is equal or lower than V . Thus, the cumulative distribution $F(V)$ is the integral of the probability density function. Thus,

$$F(V) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{V}{A}\right)^k} \quad (15)$$

The simplified case of the Weibull model is derived by approximating k as 2. This is known as the Rayleigh distribution [39].

A-6 Wake Effects Modelling Jensen Park Model

The Jansen Park model assumes that the wake behind a turbine expands linearly with downstream distance. It approximates the wake as a truncated cone (a top-hat shape) where the wind speed deficit is uniform across the wake's cross-section and zero outside of it.

Key Input Parameters

Thrust Coefficient (C_T): A dimensionless coefficient specific to each turbine model, representing the amount of momentum extracted from the wind. It varies with wind speed (typically found in the turbine's specifications)

Rotor Diameter (D): The diameter of the turbine's rotor

Wake Decay Constant (k): An empirical constant that determines the rate of wake expansion. It is dependent on site-specific atmospheric turbulence intensity. A common value for onshore applications is $k = 0.075$, but for this thesis 0.05 is assumed for k , which is appropriate for a stable, low-turbulence site [23].

The Mathematical Formulation

The model calculates the wind velocity (U_x) at a distance x downstream of a turbine for a point within the wake. Hence the following are considered

Wake Diameter: The diameter of the wake at distance x is given by

$$D_w = D + 2kx \quad (16)$$

Velocity Deficit: This is the fractional wind speed deficit at distance x . It is calculated as

$$\frac{\Delta U}{U_o} = \frac{1 - \sqrt{1 - C_T}}{\left(1 + \frac{2kx}{D}\right)^2} \quad (17)$$

Downstream Wind Speed: This is the actual wind speed experienced by a downstream turbine. It is evaluated using

$$U_x = U_o \left(1 - \frac{\Delta U}{U_o}\right) \quad (18)$$

When a turbine is affected by multiple upstream turbines, the total deficit is calculated by combining the deficits from each wake. A common method is the sum of squares of velocity deficits

$$\left(\frac{\Delta U}{U_o}\right)_{total} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\Delta U}{U_o}\right)^2} \quad (19)$$

However, the model simplifies complex fluid dynamics and may be less accurate in complex terrain or very closely spaced turbines, as it does not fully capture the effects of turbulent mixing and varying wind directions. However, for this thesis it can provide conservative estimate suitable for analysis.

A-7 Wind Measurement Techniques

Accurate knowledge of wind characteristics at prospective sites is critical for the effective planning and implementation of wind energy projects. Key information required for such analysis includes the speed and direction of prevailing winds across different time scales [24]. Ecological indicators may also assist in identifying suitable candidate sites for wind power development. While wind data from nearby meteorological stations can provide a general understanding of the wind spectrum, precise assessment requires direct measurement of wind velocity and direction at the specific site using accurate and reliable instruments. One prevalent way is illustrated by showing the top and front views of the tree trunk which is used in judging the wind in valleys, coasts and mountain terrains. It was classified by Putnam, and it was called brushing, flagging, wind throwing, clipping and carpeting. Based on these deformations, Hewson and Wade seven-point calibration describes the intensity of wind as shown in Figure 6-3. However, the final selection of a site should be made based on short-term measurements. Anemometers fitted on tall masts are used for such measurements [24]. The height of the mast may be the hub height of the turbine to avoid further correction in wind speed due surface shear. As the power is sensitive to the wind speed, it is important for the anemometer to be sensitive, reliable and properly calibrated. Based on working principle, anemometers can be classified as

1. Rotational anemometers (cup anemometers and propeller anemometers).
2. Pressure type anemometers (pressure tube anemometers, pressure plate anemometers and sphere anemometers).
3. Thermoelectric anemometers (hot wire anemometers and hot plate anemometers).
4. Phase shift anemometers (ultra-sonic anemometers and laser doppler anemometers).

Direction of wind is an important factor in the siting of a wind energy conversion system. If we receive the major share of energy available in the wind from a certain direction, it is important to avoid any directions to the wind flow from this side. Wind vanes were used to identify the wind direction. However, most of the anemometers used today can record the direction of wind along with its velocity [24].

Figure 6-3 Biological rating scales for the wind speed [37], [38]

Appendix B. Economic Modelling

B-1 Equations

Capital Recovery Factor ^[74, 31]

$$CRF = \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \quad (20)$$

Present Value of Cost ^[71, 73]

$$PVC = I_C + \left[(O\&M_c) \times \frac{1}{CRF} \right] \quad (21)$$

Levelized Cost of Electricity ^[76, 79]

$$LCOE = \frac{\text{Present value of all costs}}{\text{Present value of total energy products}} \quad (22)$$

Cash Flow ^[74, 75, 78]

$$\sum CF = \sum Revenues_n - \sum Costs_n \quad (23)$$

Economic analysis involves forecasting all project-related costs and revenues, calculating key financial indicators to assess viability, and interpreting these results from the perspective of various capital stakeholders ^[33]. Commonly used metrics for energy projects include the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE), Payback Period, Internal Rate of Return (IRR), and Net Present Value (NPV). The analysis in this thesis is conducted over a project lifetime of 20 years, which is standard for onshore wind projects.

B-2 Key Cost Factors

The total lifecycle cost of a wind farm project can be grouped into three main categories ^[79]

1. **Investment Costs:** These are all upfront costs incurred from project ideation to commercial operation. They encompass transportation, installation, civil works, legal and consultancy fees, the bill of materials (BOM), and project management. The distribution of these costs varies from project to project ^[72].
2. **Operations and Maintenance (O&M) Costs:** These are recurring costs to ensure optimal farm operation and perform repairs. They include monitoring, maintenance, insurance, land leases, taxes, and salaries. O&M costs typically increase as turbines age and are estimated to range from 1.5% to 3% of the total installed cost ^[79]. For this analysis, an O&M cost of 2.5% is assumed.

3. **Financing Costs:** Given the capital-intensive nature of wind projects, they are often funded by banks or lending institutions. The cumulative interest paid over the project's lifetime constitutes the cost of financing ^[79].

B-3 Present Value of Cost (PVC)

Recognizing that a dollar today is worth more than a dollar in the future, present value analysis is used to calculate the current worth of future transactions, accounting for the time value of money ^[85]. The Present Value of Cost (PVC) method is particularly useful for wind energy projects as it accommodates the dynamic nature of economic factors. It works by discounting all future costs and incomes to a common point in time, enabling a coherent comparison ^[80].

For scenarios involving a series of equal cash flows over a specific period, these costs are annualized using a Capital Recovery Factor (CRF). The CRF converts a present value into a stream of equal annual payments over a specified time (n), given a particular discount rate (i) ^[78].

The annual discount rate is applied to future cash flows to adjust them to their present value, thereby incorporating the time value of money and the inherent risk of the investment ^[83]. Since this risk profile, along with financing terms and ownership structure, varies for every project, the appropriate discount rate must be determined on a case-specific basis. For this thesis, a discount rate of 6.5% is adopted, reflecting the risk mitigation provided by various government and Development Finance Institution (DFI) de-risking measures.

The present value of all project expenditures over its 20-year lifetime is calculated using the inverse of the Capital Recovery Factor (CRF). Consequently, the total present value cost of the wind turbine is derived from the sum of the initial investment cost (I_c) and the present value of all future operation and maintenance costs ($O\&M_c$).

B-4 Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE)

The Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is a standard metric for comparing the cost-effectiveness of different energy technologies. As defined by IRENA, the LCOE represents the average net present cost of electricity generation per unit over the project's lifetime ^[81]. It is calculated as the ratio of the total present value of all costs to the total present value of all electricity generated.

Just as future costs are discounted to their present value, the energy generated must also be discounted. This is because the electricity sold will generate future revenue streams, the value of which must be expressed in present terms.

Currently, Nigeria lacks a fixed feed-in-tariff for renewable projects of this scale. Large projects undergo a competitive procurement process, culminating in a Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) with a predetermined price for the project's duration. The most recent PPAs for solar IPPs in Nigeria were signed in 2016 at a rate of 0.115 US\$/kWh. Subsequently, the Nigerian Bulk Electricity Trading Plc (NBET) proposed a reduced rate of 0.075 US\$/kWh in 2018, citing declining technology costs. For the calculations in this thesis, a conservative PPA rate of 0.085 US\$/kWh is assumed, with the detailed project economics presented in Table 4-5

B-5 Internal Rate of Return (IRR)

Renewable energy technologies require significant upfront capital, making its cost a major component of the project's lifecycle expenses ^[83]. For a project to be viable, the present value of its future earnings must at least equal the invested capital ^[79]. The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) is the discount rate at which the Net Present Value (NPV) of all cash flows equals zero, representing the maximum breakeven cost of capital for the project ^[86].

The output of the cash flow model is summarized in Table 5-2. The project demonstrates a positive NPV of \$28,167,113.69 and a Return on Equity of 15.05%. The pay-back period is around 10 years. Since this IRR substantially exceeds the assumed discount rate of 6.5%, the project is considered economically viable and profitable.

Appendix C. Site Considerations

One of the most complex and challenging stages in wind farm development is site selection. The objective of this phase is to identify a location that maximises net income while minimising adverse impacts, including noise, environmental effects, and excessive costs ^[60]. For these reasons, several parameters and exclusion factors are considered before siting a windfarm. Talini and Aydin listed 18 factors and grouped them into four broad groups namely: technical, economic, environmental and socio-political ^[61].

Sanchez-Lozano and his colleagues in identifying that not all sites are suited for wind farm siting defined restricted areas based on status of the given territory according local and regional policies, natural heritage and biodiversity laws, conservation laws and other such legal restrictions. These restricted areas are then subtracted from the initial area, and the remaining area is deemed legally suitable for wind farms ^[62]. They further identified four groups of general criteria namely

1. Environmental criteria
2. Orography criteria
3. Location criteria

4. Climatology criteria

Factors like agrological capacity, visual impact, wildlife impact are considered under the environmental criteria. Slope and roughness profile are addressed as orography constraints. For the location criteria, closeness to urban areas, main roads, electricity substations and powerlines are key. The last factor is how wind speed and wind direction come into play and that is the climatology criteria [62].

C-1 Environmental criteria

The proposed location of the wind farm is in Rimi, Katsina, Nigeria. It is the location of the only viable operating wind farm in Nigeria. It currently has a capacity of 10 MW. According to the land use and cover map in Figure 4-2, it is an area with a mixture of farmland with shrubs and vegetation with some few settlements. Wind power has a clear advantage over other forms of energy development as pre-existing land uses which is clearly farming and grazing can be combined with power generation with very little problem. A careful look at the land use map shows how suitable Katsina and especially Rimi is for even future expansive research (Figure 4-1). The centre of the wind farm site is located at coordinates Lat. 12.8361°N, Long. 7,6639°E

C-2 Orography Criteria

The nature of the earth's surface has a significant influence on the speed of wind over that surface. Since wind turbines are operated at a height above ground surface, the nature of the surface affects the wind speed at the wind turbine operating height. The orography criteria evaluate the nature of the site area such as the height, slope as well as roughness profile of the site.

In addition to windspeed, the nature of the site also affects the accessibility of cranes and trucks during construction, and this can affect the associated costs. Therefore, sites with slopes larger or equal to 30% are to be avoided for the purpose of wind farm projects [63].

With the help of the QGIS, we generate maps which provide information on the topography and orography of the site (Figure 4-3). The vector maps contain all the important information about Lambda Rimi. Our site is mostly a farming area, with few restricted areas, settlements and obstacles. It falls in the roughness class II. Typical exponent α for open/agricultural (Class II) is around 0.14–0.20 [63]. For purpose of uniformity, 0.14 was used in this thesis.

C-3 Location criteria

The location criteria subsume mainly three important factors namely: proximity to access roads, proximity to the power grid and proximity to consumers. To reduce the cost of new access roads and to avoid soil sealing, wind farms are located as close as possible to the existing road network. In addition, these roads must have a minimum width of 4 m and a solid pavement ^[59].

Our wind farm site as shown in is near the main access road that moves across two states (Kano and Kaduna) and leading to Niger Republic. Other secondary and tertiary roads are in proximity to the wind farm site. By land measurements, the width of the roads is over 6 m and is of a solid pavement (Figure 4-4). This is an advantage that an access road already exists and could be refurbished if needed.

C-4 Climatology criteria

The climatology i.e., the average wind speed, in each area is a key determinant of the economic performance of a wind farm. For this reason, the climatology criteria are the most important criteria to consider before locating a wind farm ^[28, 59]. An initial examination of the Rimi LGA was done at 10, 100 and 150 m, showing its suitability for a large wind power generation.

For this thesis, we were unable to take wind speed measurements at the site and had to use hourly data from the NASA POWER wind data site. Before investing in any project, it is always better and more diligent to use wind data from measurements taken onsite. Nonetheless, wind data from Global Wind Atlas and NASA POWER have been declared of high quality, accurate and representative of the site conditions, and reliable after validation and are therefore suitable for our purpose.

A generalized wind climate (GWC) data which contains the terrain-independent (uniform surface roughness and atmospheric conditions as those of the measuring position) wind climate of the wind farm site is downloaded from the Global Wind Atlas to be used for the simulation (Figure 4-6)

C-5 Wind Turbine Datasheet

GE Renewable Energy

Referenzertrag GE 5.3-158

		Leistungskurve		
		V _{Wind} in m/s	P _{Wsk} in kW	cp
Auftraggeber:	GE Wind Energy GmbH	3.0	88	0.27
WEA-Typ:	GE 5.3-158	3.5	186	0.36
Hersteller:	GE Wind Energy GmbH	4.0	310	0.40
Nennleistung:	5300 kW	4.5	466	0.43
Rotorkreisfläche:	19.607 m ²	5.0	657	0.44
Abschaltwindgeschwindigkeit:	22 m/s	5.5	892	0.45
Messbericht:		6.0	1168	0.45
Messinstitut:		6.5	1496	0.45
Messort:		7.0	1876	0.46
Berichtsdatum:		7.5	2303	0.45
Richtlinie:	Technische Richtlinie für Windkraftanlagen, Teil 5, Rev. 7	8.0	2761	0.45
EEG-konform:	Nein (basis Theoretische Kennlinie, Rev. 02)	8.5	3227	0.44
Korrekturen:	Nein	9.0	3668	0.42
		9.5	4075	0.40
		10.0	4452	0.37
		10.5	4762	0.34
		11.0	4998	0.31
		11.5	5165	0.28
		12.0	5253	0.25
		12.5	5298	0.23
		13.0	5300	0.20
		13.5	5300	0.18
		14.0	5300	0.16
		14.5	5300	0.14
		15.0	5300	0.13
		15,0-cutout	5300	0,04-0,12

Berechneter Referenzertrag	
Nabenhöhe	Referenzertrag EEG 2017
in m	in MWh
101	82,242
120,9	88,745
149	96,365
161	99,195

Anmerkungen bzgl. der Eignung für das EEG
(Zutreffendes ist angekreuzt)

- Die verwendete Leistungskurve wurde nach der Technischen Richtlinie für Windenergieanlagen (TR) Teil 2 oder MEASNET- Richtlinie oder nach einer anderen allgemein anerkannten Regel der Technik ermittelt unter Berücksichtigung der Ergänzungen der TR Teil 5. Die ausgewiesenen Referenzerträge sind uneingeschränkt für Anlagen gleichen Typs nutzbar.
- Die verwendete Leistungskurve wurde nach einem vergleichbaren Verfahren vor dem 01.01.2000 ermittelt. Die ausgewiesenen Referenzerträge sind nur zu verwenden, wenn mit der Errichtung von Anlagen des Typs nach dem 31.12.2001 im Geltungsbereich des EEG nicht mehr begonnen wurde.
- Die verwendete Leistungskurve wurde aus den Konstruktionsunterlagen des Anlagentyps ermittelt. Die ausgewiesenen Referenzerträge sind nur zu verwenden, wenn Anlagen des Typs nach dem 01.04.2000 im Geltungsbereich des EEG nicht mehr in Betrieb genommen worden sind.
- Die hier angegebenen Referenzenergieerträge erfüllen nicht alle Bedingungen des Erneuerbaren-Energien-Gesetzes. Die Berechnungen sind auf Basis der berechneten Leistungskennlinie durchgeführt worden und sind daher als Grundlage für die Ermittlung der Laufzeit der erhöhten Vergütung nicht geeignet.

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